

Annex: 2

PSYCHOSOCIAL INTERVENTIONS

Landscape of psychological and social interventions for anxiety, depression and psychosis and recommendations for investment to advance the field.

June 2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ART THERAPY.....	1
COGNITIVE BEHAVIOURAL INTERVENTION FOR TRAUMA IN SCHOOLS (CBITS)	11
EXERCISE AND THERAPY.....	18
FAMILY THERAPY	26
SHAMIRI INTERVENTION PROGRAMME	32
SKILLS TRAINING IN AFFECTIVE AND INTERPERSONAL REGULATION FOR ADOLESCENTS (STAIR - A).....	40
PEER SUPPORT (AS PER USING PEER SUPPORT IN DEVELOPING EMPOWERING MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES PROJECT - UPSIDES)	50

ART THERAPY

Pipeline stage: Ideate

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Lecturer in Arts and Play Therapy as well as an activist
- Psychiatrist, MHPSS Programme Coordinator

Target disorders:

Art therapy has applicability in psychosis, schizophrenia, anxiety, depression, PTSD, as well as for addiction disorders and chronic health issues.

Overview of intervention:

Art therapy is a form of psychotherapy that utilises artistic expression as a primary means of communication and emotional processing, which is grounded in the belief that creative artistic processes can facilitate healing and psychological well-being (Weller, 1991). Art therapy uses art as the primary mode of expression, alongside talking with an art therapist. It aims to reduce distress and improve social, emotional and mental health by promoting insight, self-compassion and a sense of agency and self-worth. This definition highlights the dual nature of art therapy, encompassing both the therapeutic process of creating art and the expressive potential of art itself.

Intervention overview:

Art therapy is a versatile and adaptable therapeutic modality used in a wide range of contexts, from mental health treatment to rehabilitation and community settings. Its application in mental health treatment has been well documented, where it is employed to help individuals express emotions, process trauma and divert responses to it, and manage psychological symptoms.

In rehabilitation settings, art therapy is increasingly used to aid recovery from physical and neurological conditions. For example, it has been shown to support individuals recovering from strokes or traumatic brain injuries by improving cognitive function, motor skills, and emotional well-being (Lo et al., 2018). Art therapy offers a nonverbal way for individuals to reconnect with themselves and their surroundings, helping them regain a sense of identity and purpose after physical trauma (Karkou & Sanderson, 2006).

Moreover, art therapy has also found its place in community settings, particularly in working with marginalised or vulnerable populations, such as refugees, migrants, or at-risk youth. In these settings, art therapy is used not only as a form of individual therapy but also as a tool for building community connections and promoting social cohesion. By engaging in collective art-making processes, participants can share their experiences and build a sense of belonging and solidarity (Ottemiller & Awais, 2016). Art-based interventions in community settings can also serve as a means of addressing cultural and societal issues, providing opportunities for healing and dialogue through creative expression (Hinz, 2019).

Scope:

Art therapy continues to evolve as both a clinical and community-based intervention and has application to all target conditions. This deep dive does not focus on any particular art form (e.g. drawing or painting) but considers art generally.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The development of art therapy interventions is rooted in both theoretical frameworks and practical considerations aimed at addressing the unique emotional and psychological needs of individuals. The theory of change in art therapy is typically grounded in the understanding that creative expression facilitates emotional processing, self-reflection, response transformation, and recovery. Art therapists draw on a variety of models, such as the Expressive Therapies Continuum, which emphasises the interaction between the cognitive, emotional, and sensory aspects of the art-making process, helping individuals externalise and make sense of internal experiences (Kagin & Lusebrink, 1978). In practice, art therapy interventions are customised to meet the needs of specific populations, from individuals with trauma and mental health disorders to those in rehabilitation and community settings. The intervention typically begins with a safe, structured environment in which individuals are encouraged to engage in art-making activities, whether through drawing, painting, sculpture, or other forms of creative expression. These activities are not only therapeutic in nature but also serve as a means of communication, particularly for individuals who struggle with verbal expression.

In terms of intervention development, therapists often engage in ongoing assessment, adjusting the interventions to align with the evolving needs of the participants, ensuring that the therapeutic goals of emotional processing, skill development, and self-expression are being met. For example, art therapy may initially aim to reduce anxiety, but as the therapy progresses, goals may shift toward developing greater emotional resilience or improving social interactions (de Witte et al., 2021).

Barriers and Facilitators to Development and Implementation

The successful development and implementation of art therapy interventions face several barriers and facilitators. One significant barrier is the lack of trained art therapists, particularly in low-resource settings. Without adequate training, art therapy cannot be delivered effectively, and its potential benefits may not be realised. In addition, cultural differences can present challenges in the design and implementation of art-based interventions, as art-making traditions and interpretations vary widely across different cultures. Therefore, cultural sensitivity and adaptability are crucial in ensuring the relevance and effectiveness of art therapy across diverse populations. Another barrier is the misconception that art therapy is only for those with artistic ability, which can prevent individuals from engaging in the therapeutic process (Zubala et al., 2023). On the other hand, facilitators to the development of art therapy include the increasing recognition of its benefits in mental health, rehabilitation, and community settings. As research on the efficacy and cost-effectiveness of art therapy grows, there is greater support for its inclusion in healthcare systems. Additionally, the non-verbal nature of art therapy can be particularly helpful in settings where verbal communication is difficult or stigmatised, such as with individuals suffering from trauma or from marginalised communities. With continued advocacy, training, and research, these barriers can be overcome, enhancing the accessibility and impact of art therapy interventions.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

A large-scale literature review of 413 studies has confirmed that art therapy alleviates mental health symptoms across a wide range of conditions, including depression, anxiety, cognitive impairments, dementia, schizophrenia, and autism. However, the effectiveness of expressive therapies such as art therapy varies significantly depending on the specific art method used, the population being treated, and the target condition. This variability suggests that art therapy's impact is not uniform, and the therapeutic benefits can differ based on these factors. However, evidence suggests that if supportively offered in the presence of trained professionals, the likelihood of harm being caused is low.

In particular, art therapy has shown promise in the treatment of psychosis and related conditions. Research indicates that expressive therapies can significantly reduce the negative symptoms associated with psychosis, including those seen in schizophrenia. Crawford *et al* (2012) conducted a study with 417 participants, of whom 355 (85%) completed a two-year follow-up. The primary outcomes were overall functioning, assessed with the Global Assessment of Functioning Scale (GAF), and mental health symptoms, evaluated using the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), at 24 months. Key secondary outcomes included group attendance, social functioning, well-being, health-related quality of life, service use, and other associated costs, measured at 12 and 24 months post-randomisation. No significant differences in primary outcomes were observed across the study groups. The adjusted mean difference between art therapy and standard care at 24 months was -0.9 [95% confidence interval (CI) -3.8 to 2.1] on the GAF Scale and 0.7 [95% CI -3.1 to 4.6] on the PANSS Scale. Similarly, no significant differences were found in secondary outcomes, with the exception that participants in the activity group showed fewer positive symptoms of schizophrenia at 24 months compared to those in the art therapy group. The findings suggest that the positive effects of art therapy may be sustained for up to six months post-intervention (Crawford *et al.*, 2012). This persistence of effect indicates that art therapy may represent a valuable treatment approach within the UK healthcare system and potentially in broader contexts. However, selection and application of art-based methods remain highly dependent on clinical judgment and patient preference, with therapists often differing in the extent to which they use art and explore the artwork through verbal discussion [KD2].

A key consideration when applying art therapy in practice is the risk of re-traumatisation or emotional distress, particularly for patients with psychosis. Encouraging self-expression through art can evoke intense emotional responses, which may not be suitable for all individuals, especially those with a history of trauma or unstable mental health conditions. While concerns about distress are valid, many studies on art therapy for psychosis have been limited by small sample sizes and qualitative methodologies. This has led to a general conclusion in the literature that more rigorous research is needed to draw definitive conclusions about the efficacy of art therapy for psychotic disorders. Seminal studies like the MATISSE trial (Multicentre Evaluation of Art Therapy in Schizophrenia: Systemic Evaluation) conducted by Crawford *et al.* (2012) have accelerated the understanding of art therapy's potential but are still considered to have methodological shortcomings, limiting the broader adoption of art therapy for psychosis, primarily related to issues with study design, sample size, and the generalizability of the results.

Further supporting the potential of art therapy, a systematic review conducted by Smriti *et al.* (2021) examined 11 studies—including randomized controlled trials (RCTs), controlled trials (CTs) and experimental designs—targeting emerging adults (ages 18-28) who experienced issues with anxiety, self-esteem, and emotional expression. The average sample size across these studies was 12.5 participants, with a median of 9 participants (the smallest sample size was 1 participant, while the largest was 47 participants). Collectively, the 11 studies employed 19 measurements to assess the effects of their interventions, the majority being standardised scales (12 studies, or 63%), followed by qualitative measurements (6 studies, or 32%), and projective tests (1 study, or 5%).

The standardized scales measured single outcomes such as self-esteem (Coppersmith's Self-esteem Inventory 1990), resilience (Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale, 2003), heart rate (Heart Rate Variability, 2016), anxiety (State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, 1983; Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7-item scale, 2006), anger (State-Trait Anger Scale, 1983) and stress (Sheldon Cohen PSS-10, 2006; ELISA salivary cortisol concentrations) and multiple outcomes through the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1996), the Brief Symptom Inventory (Derogatis, 1993) and six indicators for drama therapy assessment, such as self-awareness, self-expression, interpersonal communication skills, self-cognition, social role, and decision-making (Chang, Liu, & Yang, 2019). Among the studies using observational and

interview-based methods, two analysed the content of poems in poetry therapy studies, while others included behavioural observations and participant interviews.

The review concluded that art therapy demonstrated significant improvements across psychological domains, including self-awareness, resilience, and anxiety symptoms. The art forms employed across these studies varied, including drawing, engraving, colouring mandalas, clay modelling, and free-form painting. Specifically, the combination of engraving and rational emotive behaviour therapy was found to significantly enhance self-esteem and resilience in university students ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, other forms of art-making (free-form painting, mandala colouring, clay modelling) were associated with significant reductions in anxiety ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, engaging in poetry therapy (reading, filling in gaps, collaborative writing) helped emerging adults cope with mental health issues, significantly reducing depression, anxiety, and stress ($p < 0.01$). Music therapy was also shown to significantly reduce anger and psychological symptoms ($p < 0.05$), with long-term effects on anger reduction. Finally, drama therapy applied to a group of 12 high-risk students resulted in significant improvements in self-awareness, decision-making, self-expression, interpersonal communication, self-recognition, and social role skills ($p < 0.01$).

These findings contribute to the growing body of evidence suggesting that art therapy is an effective intervention for diverse populations, including those with learning disabilities, trauma survivors, and people experiencing anxiety (Schouten et al., 2015; Van Lith, 2016).

Moreover, research suggests that art therapy can be particularly effective when combined with other therapeutic approaches, such as cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) or a solution-centred approach (Volker, 1997). The integration of these approaches with art therapy offers the possibility of addressing a broader array of psychological issues, enhancing the overall therapeutic effect.

Gaps in research and evaluation

Despite the promising findings from various studies, the evidence base for art therapy in the treatment of mental health conditions like depression, anxiety, and psychosis remains incomplete. A primary gap in the research is the heterogeneity in art therapy methodologies. As noted, the effectiveness of art therapy can vary based on the chosen art method, the characteristics of the population being treated, and the specific target condition. Further studies are needed to systematically compare the impact of different art methods (e.g., drawing vs. sculpture) to identify which approaches are most effective for particular mental health issues.

Another gap lies in the lack of large-scale, well-controlled studies, particularly with larger sample sizes and longitudinal follow-ups. Most of the existing studies on art therapy, especially in psychosis, rely on qualitative research designs and small sample groups, which limits the generalizability of their findings. Future research would benefit from more robust randomised controlled trials (RCTs) with diverse populations, particularly in the context of psychosis and depression, where the effects of art therapy can be more nuanced and complex.

Furthermore, there is a need for standardised outcome measures that can more precisely evaluate the effectiveness of art therapy across different mental health conditions. While some studies have utilised standardised scales to assess emotional expression and self-esteem, these metrics may not fully capture the nuances of the therapeutic process. Developing more specific and comprehensive tools for evaluating the impact of art therapy on symptoms of depression, anxiety, and psychosis would strengthen the evidence base and facilitate its integration into clinical practice.

Relevance to PLE:

Both systematic reviews and engagement with PLE highlight that art therapies offer an accessible, widely accepted, and empowering entry point for treatment interventions (Ford et al., 2021). PLEs particularly value artmaking as a recovery tool, appreciating its innovative, strengths-based approach that fosters self-expression and enhances control, confidence, and agency in the recovery process (Van Lith, 2015). Clients also report that art therapy is effective in reducing the negative symptoms of psychosis and schizophrenia, as well as improving mental health and social functioning (Hanevik et al., 2013). Art therapy is particularly effective for individuals who may struggle with traditional verbal therapies, such as those experiencing severe trauma, psychosis, or conditions like anxiety and depression (Malchiodi, 2012).

In addition, PLE consultations for this project emphasised the relevance of art-based therapies for conditions such as depression and anxiety, noting that these therapies tend to be more accessible than traditional therapeutic approaches. One of the interviewees notes that *"for many, traditional verbal therapies can feel inaccessible or alienating, and art therapies provide an alternative pathway for exploration and recovery. These modalities create opportunities for decolonial and non-Western approaches to therapy, embedding community-centred practices into public health"* (Stakeholder interview 1). Speaking of the importance of a person-centred approach in art therapy, another interviewee states that *"experiences of mental health disorders could be very subjective. Each of us live depression or PTSD differently because we are different, and we give different reactions to distressing or traumatic life events. Art therapy helps us process it, reveal the effectiveness of our existing responses, and how we respond to these challenges and disorders. It allows us to shape our responses in a more effective way"* (Stakeholder interview 2).

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

While there is growing interest in the potential of art therapies, reviews of the evidence show that the majority of research and application has been concentrated in high-income countries, revealing a significant gap in the exploration and implementation of art therapy in low- and middle-income settings. This presents both a challenge and an opportunity for further development and research in these regions (Uttley et al., 2015; Tjasink, 2015).

Reviews show that cost-effectiveness data for art therapy is quasi-non-existent. Uttley et al. (2015) identified only one study which measured the costs of art therapy; however, costs were estimated based on one patient (out of 357 initially enrolled). Modelling done by the authors suggests, however, that art therapy against no treatment control is cost-effective at just under £6000/QALY in the UK (assuming 42 sessions over 52 weeks at a per patient cost of £750 and willingness to pay of £20,000/QALY). However, when considering art therapy against verbal therapy, results suggest that verbal therapy dominates (art therapy remains cost-effective in less than 20% of cases). Further studies are needed to confirm this finding, as well as evidence to inform future cost-effective analyses of art therapy versus other treatments.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Art therapies provide a promising alternative to verbal therapy, offering a potentially more accessible and 'low-risk' option, especially in settings where seeking mental health support is stigmatised or culturally challenging (Stakeholder interview 2). However, significant barriers to access remain, particularly in low-income or conflict-affected regions. Training programs for art therapies are predominantly offered in high-income countries, accompanied by high tuition fees, which severely limit opportunities for practitioners in these underserved areas. Moreover, the lack of dedicated spaces such as studios or therapy centres,

along with the cost of art materials, further hinders the implementation of these therapies in resource-poor settings.

Humanitarian organisations, in response to these limitations, are increasingly incorporating art-based interventions into programmes in contexts affected by conflict, displacement, and disaster. Yet, these interventions tend to remain framed as recreational activities rather than formal therapy methods (IOM, 2022). This distinction has crucial implications for both the practice and potential impact of these interventions. Art activities like painting or mandala drawing often serve as 'access gates', offering a neutral entry point for introducing mental health services in settings where discussing mental health may be taboo. These activities can create a safe space for normalising conversations about mental health, allowing mental health professionals to engage with individuals and communities in a non-threatening way (Stakeholder interview 2).

However, while art-based recreational activities can offer emotional relief and temporary expression, they lack the depth and structure needed to achieve long-term therapeutic outcomes. Without trained facilitators and a clinically grounded understanding of how to integrate art within a therapeutic framework, these activities are unlikely to realise their full potential. They may serve as a valuable first step, but they cannot replace the comprehensive mental health support that individuals in conflict or displacement settings desperately need.

Beyond access and training challenges, the cultural adaptability of art therapies is also a key consideration. Successful implementation requires that therapists adapt their approaches to fit the local cultural context, respecting and incorporating local values, beliefs, and artistic traditions (Howie et al., 2013). This is especially important when working with communities affected by trauma, as the cultural resonance of the intervention can significantly impact its effectiveness. Additionally, language barriers and the availability of culturally appropriate materials may further complicate the delivery of art therapies in some regions.

Despite these challenges, there is growing evidence from neuroscience and psychological research supporting the integration of art therapies in healthcare and education, which indicates that, when properly implemented, these therapies can play an essential role in promoting emotional and psychological healing (Kaye-Huntington & Peterson, 2010). As such, while art therapies show considerable promise, their successful application hinges on overcoming barriers related to accessibility, cultural sensitivity, and professional training, all of which must be addressed for these interventions to reach their full therapeutic potential.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

PLE consultations highlighted the potential of art therapies, noting that these approaches allow participants to express themselves as they are and how they perceive themselves and their mental health challenges and disorders. However, the availability of training programs in expressive therapies is limited, primarily offered in high-income countries and often accompanied by steep access fees. This creates significant barriers to access, particularly for low-income countries or regions affected by conflict, disasters, and displacement (Stakeholder interview 2). Furthermore, the lack of dedicated studios or centres and the cost of purchasing art materials further hinder the widespread implementation of these therapies (Stakeholder interview 1).

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Art therapy, as an intervention across a range of mental health and rehabilitation settings, demonstrates a broad spectrum of potential, from reducing symptoms of mental health disorders to promoting emotional well-being and enhancing social functioning. Despite its versatility, the advancement and implementation

of art therapy face several barriers that have slowed its integration into clinical and community-based settings. These barriers include the limited availability of trained art therapists, particularly in low-resource environments, as well as misconceptions about the need for artistic skill to participate in therapy. Cultural differences also present a challenge, with varying interpretations of art and artistic practices that can affect how art therapy is implemented and received by different communities. Overcoming these barriers requires addressing the training gap, ensuring cultural adaptability, and dismantling myths about the nature of the therapy.

One of the most significant facilitators of art therapy's advancement is the growing body of evidence supporting its effectiveness across diverse populations and conditions. A large-scale review has demonstrated that art therapy can alleviate symptoms in conditions ranging from anxiety to schizophrenia, making it a viable adjunct or alternative to traditional therapies, particularly for individuals who struggle with verbal expression. Moreover, the non-verbal nature of art therapy makes it a valuable intervention for individuals with severe trauma, psychosis, or those from marginalised populations who may find verbal therapies difficult or stigmatising. This has driven increased support for the inclusion of art therapy in healthcare systems, especially as research continues to emphasise its cost-effectiveness and clinical utility. However, while the therapeutic promise is clear, challenges related to resource limitations, especially in low-income and conflict-affected regions, must be overcome for its full potential to be realised globally.

The theory of change underpinning art therapy focuses on the transformative power of creative expression to facilitate emotional processing, self-reflection, and healing. Art therapists tailor interventions to meet the evolving needs of individuals, but the lack of standardisation in practice and the reliance on small, qualitative studies have left some gaps in the evidence base, particularly in terms of long-term outcomes. While research on the effectiveness of art therapy in psychosis is promising, methodological weaknesses in the studies conducted so far have kept the field in a state of "emerging evidence." As a result, there is a pressing need for larger, more robust studies that can confirm the long-term benefits of art therapy across different conditions. Additionally, given the widespread acceptance and appreciation of art therapy by service users, further studies should focus on understanding patient/client experiences and outcomes to refine therapeutic approaches and improve access to treatment.

In terms of cost-effectiveness, evidence is scarce but suggestive of potential preference for art therapy when compared to wait-list control. However, the evidence is from high-income settings only and more studies are needed to compare its cost-effectiveness directly with other therapeutic modalities, particularly in non-psychotic disorders and other contexts.

The scalability of art therapy faces several constraints, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where training programs, resources, and access to materials are limited. However, art therapy's low-risk, accessible nature makes it an appealing option, especially where the non-verbal nature of the therapy and its ability to foster expression in non-stigmatising environments can help bridge significant gaps in mental health care.

Further, there is evidence of applicability to humanitarian contexts, such as conflict zones or refugee camps, where mental health support is scarce and often stigmatised. In these settings, art-based activities can serve as an entry point for engaging individuals with mental health services, though these activities must be seen as part of a broader, more comprehensive therapeutic framework to achieve sustained results. Cultural sensitivity is critical in such interventions, as art therapy must respect local traditions and values to be truly effective.

Lastly, the lessons learned from the development and implementation of art therapy interventions highlight the importance of addressing systemic barriers, ensuring cultural relevance, and improving accessibility. Continued advocacy, investment in training, and robust research are needed to solidify art therapy as a mainstream therapeutic modality. With these efforts, art therapy can expand its reach and effectiveness, offering a valuable, creative alternative to traditional therapeutic methods for individuals across diverse contexts and conditions.

Recommendations for investment:

To ensure the successful advancement and widespread adoption of art therapy as a therapeutic modality, several targeted recommendations are necessary. These recommendations are grounded in the lessons learned from current practices, challenges faced in implementation, and the evolving research landscape.

Research Recommendations

- **Expand and standardise training programs for art therapists in low-resource settings.** One of the most significant barriers to the implementation of art therapy is the lack of adequately trained professionals, particularly in low-resource and low-income settings. To address this, it is critical to develop and expand training programs specifically designed for these regions. This can be achieved by partnering with PLE as well as academics, healthcare systems, and community organisations to create affordable, context-sensitive curricula that can be adapted to local needs. The International Expressive Arts Therapy Association could be a leader in such endeavours. Additionally, online training platforms and virtual workshops should be utilised to bridge geographical gaps and provide a more cost-effective means of training. Offering scholarships or subsidising tuition fees for trainees from low-income countries or conflict-affected regions can further increase accessibility and ensure that qualified professionals are equipped to deliver effective art therapy.
- **Investigate integration of art therapy into mental health and rehabilitation policy frameworks.** While art therapy has shown promise in numerous studies, its integration into healthcare systems is still limited, particularly outside high-income countries. To overcome this, investment is needed to identify how governments and international organisations can include art therapy in national mental health policies. Additionally, the growing evidence base around art therapy's efficacy should be presented to key stakeholders to ensure its recognition as a legitimate, cost-effective therapeutic option that can complement traditional therapies.
- **Support for conducting larger, methodologically rigorous research studies.** Despite the growing body of evidence supporting the effectiveness of art therapy, the field still lacks large-scale, rigorous studies, particularly with long-term follow-up and inclusion of quantitative outcome measurements, including costs and cost-effectiveness. There is an urgent need to conduct randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and longitudinal studies to provide more definitive evidence of its efficacy across diverse populations and conditions. These studies should focus on specific mental health disorders, such as psychosis and schizophrenia, as well as trauma-related conditions, to confirm the therapeutic benefits and further refine intervention techniques. Moreover, a comprehensive approach that combines both qualitative and quantitative methodologies will help capture both the subjective experiences of clients and measurable clinical outcomes, as well as costs. Research should also explore the potential of integrating art therapy with other therapeutic modalities, such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), to examine synergistic effects.
- **Development of culturally appropriate art therapy interventions.** Given the diverse cultural backgrounds of individuals seeking art therapy, it is critical that interventions are culturally sensitive

and tailored to the specific needs of each population. Therapists should undergo cultural competency training to better understand and incorporate local artistic traditions, values, and communication styles into the therapeutic process. This is especially important when working with marginalised or displaced populations, such as refugees or those affected by trauma in conflict zones. Collaboration with local cultural experts and community leaders is essential to ensuring that art therapy resonates with the community's values and addresses their unique emotional and psychological needs. In addition, culturally appropriate materials and art forms should be provided to enhance the therapeutic process and ensure that participants feel understood and respected.

Ecosystems Recommendations

- **Address resource and infrastructure challenges in low-income and conflict-affected areas.** For art therapy to be implemented effectively in low-income or conflict-affected regions, significant investments in infrastructure and resources are necessary. This includes creating dedicated spaces for therapy, such as community art centres or therapy studios, where individuals can engage in creative expression in a supportive and safe environment. Additionally, efforts must be made to reduce the cost of art materials, either by sourcing affordable, locally available recycled supplies or by working with international organisations to provide donations of materials. Humanitarian agencies should also expand their use of art-based interventions beyond recreational activities, providing structured art therapy programs that are grounded in clinical practice. Training facilitators in these settings on the difference between art as a recreational activity and as a therapeutic tool will be key to maximising the potential impact of these interventions.
- **Examine the use of art therapy methods as a gateway to broader mental health services.** Art therapy's non-verbal nature makes it an excellent entry point for individuals who may be reluctant to seek traditional mental health support due to stigma, fear, or language barriers. In settings where mental health discussions are stigmatised, art therapy can serve as a bridge, allowing individuals to engage in emotional expression without the need for verbal communication. This is particularly crucial in marginalised or underserved communities. How to use art therapy methods as a potential initial engagement or screening tool has not been researched.

Key references:

- Crawford, M.J., Killapsy, H., Kalaitzaki, E., Barrett, B., Byford, S., Patterson, S., Soteriou, T., O'Neill, F.A., Clayton, K., Maratos, A., Barnes, T.R., Osborn, D., Johnson, T., King, M., Tyrer, P., Waller, D. 2012. Group art therapy as an adjunctive treatment for people with schizophrenia: a randomised control trial (MATISSE). *Health Technology Assessment* 16(8): doi: 10.3310/hta16080
- de Witte, M., Orkibi, H., Zarate, R., Karkou, V., Sajnani, N., Malhotra, B., Ho, R. T. H., Kaimal, G., Baker, F. A., & Koch, S. C. (2021). From Therapeutic Factors to Mechanisms of Change in the Creative Arts Therapies: A Scoping Review. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 678397. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.678397>
- Ford, E., George, N., Holland, E., Maher, S., Maree, L., Naylor, K., Rossel, K., & Wake, J. (2021). Seven lived experience stories of making meaning using art therapy. *International Journal of Art Therapy*, 26(1–2), 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17454832.2021.1893771>
- Hanevik, H., Hestad, K.A., Lien, L., Teglbjaerg, H.S., Danbolt, L.J. 2013. Expressive art therapy for psychosis: A multiple case study. *The Arts in Psychotherapy* 40:312-321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2013.05.011>
- Hinz, L.D. (2019). *Expressive Therapies Continuum: A Framework for Using Art in Therapy* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429299339>
- Kagin, S. L., & Lusebrink, V. B. (1978). The expressive therapies continuum. *Art Psychotherapy*, 5(4), 171–180. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-9092\(78\)90031-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-9092(78)90031-5)
- Karkou, V., & Sanderson, P. (2006). Arts therapies: A research-based map of the field. *International Journal of Art Therapy*, 11(2), 35-47. Doi: 10.1016/B978-0-443-07256-7.X5001-3
- Kaye-Huntington, S., & Peterson, C. C. (2010). Art therapy in the context of creative expressive therapies. In D. A. Monti & B. D. Beitman (Eds.), *Integrative psychiatry* (pp. 86–110). Oxford University Press.

- Lo, T. L. T., Lee, J. L. C., & Ho, R. T. H. (2018). Creative Arts-Based Therapies for Stroke Survivors: A Qualitative Systematic Review. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1646. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01646>
- Malchiodi, C. A. (2012). *Handbook of art therapy*. Guilford Press.
- Ottemiller, D. D., & Awais, Y. J. (2016). A model for art therapists in community-based practice. *Art Therapy*, 33(3), 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421656.2016.1199245>
- International Organization for Migration (IOM). 2022. *Manual on Community-based Mental Health and Psychosocial Support in Emergencies and Displacement - Second Edition*. IOM, Geneva; UNHCR (2022). *Field Brief: Establishment of Multi-purpose Youth-Friendly Centres for Young Refugees in Nepal*.
- Schouten, K. A., De Niet, G. J., Knipscheer, J. W., Kleber, R. J., & Hutschemaekers, G. J. M. (2014). The effectiveness of art therapy in the treatment of traumatized adults. *Trauma Violence & Abuse*, 16(2), 220–228. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524838014555032>
- Smriti, D; Ambulkar, S; Meng, Q; Kaimal, G; Ramotar, K; Park, S; Huh-Yoo, J. (2021). Creative arts therapies for the mental health of emerging adults: A systematic review. *The Arts in Psychotherapy*, 77, 101861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2021.101861>
- Uttley, L., Scope, A., Stevenson, M., Rawdin, A., Taylor Buck, E., Sutton, A., Stevens, J., Kaltenthaler, E., Dent-Brown, K., & Wood, C. (2015). Systematic review and economic modelling of the clinical effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of art therapy among people with non-psychotic mental health disorders. *Health technology assessment (Winchester, England)*, 19(18), 1–vi. <https://doi.org/10.3310/hta19180>
- Uttley, L., Stevenson, M., Scope, A. et al. The clinical and cost effectiveness of group art therapy for people with non-psychotic mental health disorders: a systematic review and cost-effectiveness analysis. *BMC Psychiatry* 15, 151 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-015-0528-4>
- Tjasink, M., Keiller, E., Stephens, M., Carr, C. E., & Priebe, S. (2023). Art therapy-based interventions to address burnout and psychosocial distress in healthcare workers—a systematic review. *BMC Health Services Research*, 23, 1059. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09958-8>
- Van Lith, T. (2015). *Art therapy in mental health: A systematic review of approaches and practices*. *The Arts in Psychotherapy*, 47, 9–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2015.09.003>
- Volker, C. A. (1997). *Treatment of Sexual Assault Survivors Utilizing Cognitive Therapy and Art Therapy* (Publication No. 304392082) [Doctoral Dissertation, California Institute of Integral Studies]. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/treatment-sexual-assault-survivors-utilizing/docview/304392082/se-2?accountid=10910>.
- Waller, D. (1991). *Becoming a profession: A history of art therapy 1940-82*. Routledge, London, UK.
- Zubala, A., Kennell, N., MacInnes, C., MacInnes, M., & Malcolm, M. (2023). Online art therapy pilot in the western isles of Scotland: a feasibility and acceptability study of a novel service in a rural community. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1193445>

COGNITIVE BEHAVIOURAL INTERVENTION FOR TRAUMA IN SCHOOLS (CBITS)

Pipeline stage: Improve and Test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Developer of CBITS, USA
- Professor of Psychiatry, USA
- Grantee supporting CBITS implementation across a European country

Target disorders:

The intervention aims to assist adolescents who have prior trauma exposure and are likely to be affected by PTSD. Diagnosis is not a prerequisite for receiving the intervention, although adolescents are usually screened for trauma exposure and PTSD symptoms prior to accessing CBITS. The intervention is not suitable for crisis support or intensive treatment, or for use with adolescents affected by severe behavioural problems or severe cognitive impairments.

Overview of intervention:

CBITS is a school-based programme that provides both group and individual sessions to help child and adolescent students (8-15) cope with trauma. It aims to reduce symptoms of PTSD and co-occurring depression and behavioural challenges. The programme consists of 10 group sessions for students (weekly, 45 minutes), 1-3 individual student sessions (when needed, 30 minutes), 2-3 caregiver sessions, and an educational session for teachers.

Students who have experienced distressing events, such as community or school violence, accidents, physical abuse, exposure to climate disasters, or domestic violence, are the target group. Prior to receiving CBITS, students usually undergo screening for traumatic events exposure and PTSD associated symptoms. Screening should be implemented only 3-6 months post-traumatic event in order to capture those students experiencing enduring challenges and should be done by interview, rather than relying on self-reported measures. The programme specifically targets those with above moderate symptoms.

The programme is fully delivered in school settings but requires delivery by trained personnel (with experience of CBT and/or trauma therapy). Even where education professionals can be trained in the above, further support during CBITS implementation is highly recommended by the developers.

Scope:

This deep dive explores CBITS in relation to PTSD; lessons from the development and adaptation of the intervention for schools may also inform other interventions for depression and anxiety disorders. Different adaptations of the programme exist, including for younger age-groups (Bounce Back), for delivery via nonclinical personnel (Support for Students Exposed to Trauma - SSET) and a third version of CBITS with a focus on family and caregiver functioning. We will refer to these, particularly SSET – as relevant throughout.

Intervention development and theory of change:

CBITS was originally developed in the USA, drawing on a community-partnered research approach. The programme originated from a collaboration between the Los Angeles Unified School District, the University of California, Los Angeles, and RAND Corporation. CBITS is tailored for delivery within the school environment in order to ensure wide accessibility to students who may be in need but may face additional barriers to access (e.g. due to low socio-economic background and lack of resources).

CBITS directly draws on principles of trauma adaptation and trauma-informed therapies (including CBT). The intervention helps students manage trauma by addressing thoughts, feelings, and behaviours. It teaches students to recognise and challenge negative thinking, regulate distress, and reduce avoidance of trauma reminders. Students learn relaxation techniques, problem-solving skills, and how to take positive action in difficult situations. In group sessions, students are also introduced to writing, thinking and talking exercises which encourage them to process their experiences in a safe setting, reducing anxiety over time. Creating a trauma narrative allows students to better understand their experiences, making distressing thoughts less disruptive. Where it is safe to do so, the programme also encourages students to face avoided people, places, or situations linked to their trauma, helping them regain a sense of control and reduce anxiety through gradual exposure. PTSD and depression symptom reduction, as well as enhanced control, are then noted to influence school attendance and performance and family and community relationships.

At the prototype stage and the improve and test stage, CBITS was first tested in a quasi-experimental pilot study, followed by a randomised controlled trial, both demonstrating significant reductions in PTSD and depression symptoms among participating students. The programme was refined based on these findings and subsequently expanded to other school settings in the USA. The expansion process required careful adaptation to different school environments, stakeholder engagement, and integration into existing educational frameworks.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Evidence supporting the effectiveness of CBITS has been documented in several U.S.-based trials. The earliest, conducted by Kataoka et al. (2003) with Latino immigrant students, demonstrated promising results. Further studies then specifically investigated the impact of early versus delayed intervention in general school populations to determine the optimal timing for CBITS after trauma. Stein et al. (2003) compared CBITS (n=61) to a waitlist control (n=65), finding significant benefits at three months for PTSD (8.9 vs. 15.5; adjusted mean difference, -7.0; 95% CI, -10.8 to -3.2), depression (9.4 vs. 12.7; adjusted mean difference, -3.4; 95% CI, -6.5 to -0.4), and psychosocial dysfunction (12.5 vs. 16.5; adjusted mean difference, -6.4; 95% CI, -10.4 to -2.3). However, after all participants received CBITS, mental health outcomes were similar across groups, though Kataoka et al. (2011) noted potential academic benefits to early intervention.

Jaycox et al. (2010) examined CBITS (n=58) compared to trauma-focused CBT (n=60) following Hurricane Katrina. While both groups showed similar PTSD outcomes at 10 months, trauma-focused CBT had a slight advantage (mean PTSD score: 12 vs. 15.8). However, accessibility differed significantly—98% of students accessed and 91% completed CBITS, compared to just 37% accessing and 31% completing trauma-focused CBT in clinical settings.

Goodkind et al. (2010) evaluated a CBITS adaptation for American Indian populations, highlighting challenges with feasibility, particularly low acceptability of screening and high levels of detected need. Despite these barriers, CBITS effectively reduced PTSD symptoms (by 2.8 points per three-month interval), anxiety (by 1 point per month), and depression (by 0.5 points per month). Participants reported

finding the intervention beneficial and enjoyable, and Morsette et al. (2009) noted an increase in educators' confidence in addressing trauma.

Despite the existence of several trials confirming the promise of CBITS, the evidence base is underdeveloped and generally appears at high risk of potential bias. For example, in many of the above-quoted trials, outcome assessment was not blinded, and it is likely that allocation was also not fully concealed and could have been influenced. More robust, large-scale studies, also focusing on the SSET approach to CBITS, are needed. In relation to the latter in particular, one pilot test found slight reductions in trauma symptoms overall, with the greatest benefits for students with severe initial symptoms. Students and parents expressed high satisfaction with the program, and while teachers noted minor behavioural improvements, parents did not (Stein et al, 2011).

Outside the U.S., research on CBITS is scarce. One study, Pfeiffer et al. (2024), sets out plans for CBITS implementation and evaluation in Germany. Despite CBITS developers and trainers noting implementation across several countries, there is no firm evidence documented from these settings. Interviewees generally noted promising experiences and effects across settings.

Relevance to PLE:

Engagement with individuals with lived experience seems to have been facilitated through partnerships with school personnel, parents, and community organisations, ensuring cultural and contextual relevance of CBITS. The developers note in several documents that continuous evaluation of CBITS as implemented, including feedback from children and adolescents themselves, is used to further refine guidance and materials. The developers emphasise the importance of cultural relevance and adaptability in CBITS while maintaining fidelity to core treatment concepts. They suggest using familiar figures from TV shows, sports, history, and music (e.g., *That's So Raven*, Kobe Bryant, Rosa Parks) to illustrate key therapeutic ideas like cognition and problem-solving. Additionally, culturally significant practices, such as burning sweet grass during relaxation exercises for Native American groups, can be incorporated. Training includes discussions on cultural sensitivity, ensuring that children's beliefs—such as belief in ghosts—are respected rather than dismissed. The overarching goal is to implement CBITS in a way that aligns with the backgrounds and experiences of the children it serves while preserving the integrity of the intervention.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Cost-effectiveness evidence on CBITS is not available. CBITS is a manualised intervention, with the intervention manual freely available online or in print for US\$32. However, training and adaptation are noted to be facilitated by the CBITS website (<https://cbitsprogram.org/>). There are options to complete self-directed online asynchronous learning - this involves a 5-hour interactive course, which provides a certificate of completion (US\$39/user with bulk discounts available) or to have 12 hours of in-service training (\$7500 for training plus cost of travel). The latter training is for 15 trainees and can be delivered virtually as well. Consultations cost \$350/hour outside of the above. Costs for SSET are slightly lower and estimated at \$4300/ trainer for 20 trainees in addition to expenses. Overall, these costs do not cover implementation or supervision; costs that are likely to be substantive in practice, as human resource costs and any access support costs must be considered. Bounce Back notes cost at \$20,000 for training up to 15 trainees (12 hours live training or 5 hours on demand) plus time to observe group work and implementation of one round; each follow-up training and support is a further \$7500 (Langley and Jaycox 2024).

Context, applicability and scalability:

The intervention has been implemented across several USA states, with developers noting that schools in Lithuania, China, Guyana and Japan have also implemented CBITS– although evidence from these could not be located. CBITS was tailored for different cultural and socio-economic backgrounds, with materials available in Spanish initially and now also Arabic, and structured flexibility for implementation in varied school settings. Different versions of CBITS have also been developed to ensure broader applicability and scalability – e.g. to other age groups (Bounce Back) or to delivery via nonclinical personnel (SSET).

Thomas et al (2022) reviewed the literature on trauma-focused CBT implementation in children and youth in LMICs affected by conflict. While they do not identify any study focused on CBITS, they identify three studies that use similar group-based delivery mechanisms in schools in the DRC and note that across studies with group delivery, generally, there has been evidence of effectiveness in PTSD symptom reduction. MhGAP (WHO 2023) further indicates that school-based interventions show potential as an effective way to deliver large-scale preventive and promotive programs, though further cost analysis is required.

It is important to note that both for CBITS and other group-based interventions, delivery adaptations may be needed depending on trauma type. For example, for sexual trauma, it may be that gender specific groups need to be organised, that additional support may be needed and/or that a safe space/referral needs to be put in place.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

CBITS was specifically developed for school implementation to overcome inequities in access to PTSD support for children and adolescents of lower socio-economic background. Evidence supports the fact that CBITS proves more accessible and that cultural adaptations are appreciated and make the programme impactful. However, the evidence base is scarce and at high risk of bias, and no studies specifically focused on equity have been conducted.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Despite its structured design and evidence base in the United States, the CBITS faces several significant barriers to broader implementation and scaling, particularly in LMICs. A key barrier is the limited evidence on its effectiveness outside the U.S., particularly for adapted versions. While a structured manual is available and CBITS training has been disseminated widely, the absence of context-specific data impedes further innovation and adaptation.

Implementation challenges are substantial, particularly in school-based settings, which CBITS relies on. These challenges are magnified in LMICs, where educational infrastructure may be less developed, school attendance is often inconsistent, and resources for mental health support are limited. Logistical constraints such as inadequate space, scheduling conflicts, and competing academic demands hinder smooth integration into school routines. Similar barriers were echoed in both U.S. and international settings, including Lithuania, as noted by one interviewee. Staff capacity and buy-in also pose obstacles. Competing priorities among school staff and clinicians, staff turnover, and limited time to engage with additional programmes have all impacted implementation fidelity. Some school personnel were reluctant to adopt CBITS, questioning its alignment with academic goals and expressing concern about potential stigma, such as children being identified as trauma-exposed when removed from class. Additionally, clinicians often prioritised more urgent trauma-related cases (e.g., sexual health concerns), diverting time from CBITS delivery.

Parental consent and engagement present another major barrier (as noted by Nadeem et al, 2011). In many communities, especially those with legal or cultural sensitivities around mental health, obtaining parental consent can limit student participation. In some cases, parental involvement may even be unsafe for children. Low attendance at parent sessions and general disengagement further reduce programme impact.

Finally, financial constraints and sustainability are ongoing issues. Costed support for training and supervision may be prohibitive, particularly without reliable funding or integration into national educational or health systems. As noted by both researchers and implementers, sustainable financing and compliance with regulatory frameworks are necessary for long-term continuity.

For LMICs, challenges such as irregular school attendance, under-resourced systems, and limited mental health personnel remain critical barriers. As Grande et al. (2023) point out, findings from specific contexts (e.g., Iran) may not generalise to the broader diversity of LMICs. Any efforts to scale CBITS in these settings must account for the need for ongoing supervision, clinician training, and routine adaptation. SSET (Support for Students Exposed to Trauma), an adaptation of CBITS for lower-resource contexts, shows promise but remains under-researched.

Despite these barriers, several factors consistently emerge as **facilitators** of successful CBITS implementation (Ngo et al, 2008). CBITS' clear implementation roadmap—including planning, training, and ongoing supervision—was highly valued by implementers, as remarked both in interviews and literature. Its flexible, modular design allows for cultural and contextual adaptation while maintaining fidelity to the core components.

The co-development model, involving educators, clinicians, and community stakeholders from the outset, has ensured that CBITS is grounded in school contexts and responsive to local needs. This has helped establish strong partnerships and secured additional resources in some cases, often through collaboration with community-based organisations.

Endorsement from district leaders, school principals, and senior staff has been critical in mobilising resources and building staff buy-in. Such leadership also helps align CBITS with institutional priorities. When positive student outcomes were measured and reported, schools were better able to justify continued investment and expansion of the programme.

Strong school administrative support plays a crucial role in integrating CBITS into existing mental health services. Embedding the programme within school-based mental health initiatives enhances both accessibility and sustainability. Additionally, structured training programs for providers help maintain fidelity to the model while allowing for necessary adaptations to fit local contexts. Interviewees noted that trainers were generous with their time and invested in ensuring successful delivery. Their ongoing mentorship and support beyond initial training helped improve confidence and fidelity among providers.

Recommendations for investment:

To support the advancement of CBITS and similar school-based mental health interventions, particularly in LMICs, several investment priorities emerge.

Research Recommendations

- **Invest in high-quality, large-scale hybrid research to evaluate CBITS in diverse settings.** There is a pressing need for more rigorous research into the effectiveness, adaptability, fidelity and equity of access and outcomes of CBITS beyond the United States. Future research should include well-powered, methodologically robust hybrid trials conducted in LMICs. These studies should be conducted across a variety of cultural, economic, and educational settings and also investigate

strategies to overcome known barriers such as school scheduling constraints, staff turnover, and limited parental engagement, while identifying conditions that support programme sustainability. Comparative studies are also needed—both between CBITS and other psychosocial interventions (e.g. child-friendly spaces in humanitarian settings), and across different delivery modalities, such as clinical vs. non-clinical staff, including through the SSET model.

- **Fund cost-effectiveness research.** CBITS lacks formal cost-effectiveness data, which limits its scalability in health and education systems. Investment should support studies that quantify the full costs of delivery—including training, supervision, and human resource time—and evaluate how these costs compare to alternative interventions as noted above.
- **Explore modular or transdiagnostic applications of CBITS content.** While CBITS is focused on trauma-related disorders, its cognitive behavioural foundations offer potential for broader application. Investment in the development of modular versions—incorporating elements that address anxiety, depression, or other psychosocial challenges—could enhance the programme’s flexibility and relevance in diverse school settings. Lessons from Bounce Back (for younger children) and family-focused adaptations should be incorporated into this work.

Ecosystems Recommendations

- **Support context-specific adaptation and piloting in LMICs and humanitarian settings.** Although CBITS was designed for underserved populations, further adaptation is essential to ensure cultural and contextual relevance across new settings. Investment should support adaptation through co-production with local stakeholders—including students, caregivers, educators, and community leaders—to tailor materials, delivery approaches, and group structures to local norms and trauma profiles. For example, trauma type may require adaptations such as gender-specific groups or strengthened referral systems for sexual violence survivors. The SSET model, designed for lower-resource delivery, should be prioritised for piloting in LMICs where access to trained clinicians is limited. Adaptations for humanitarian settings may also be appropriate, particularly when considering integration of interventions like CBITS into responses following natural disasters.
- **Expand affordable and scalable training and supervision models for interventions such as CBITS.** Cost and access to training remain key barriers to implementation of interventions such as CBITS, especially in resource-constrained settings. Investment is needed to expand low-cost, scalable training platforms such as mobile-first or offline-compatible online courses. Localised “train-the-trainer” approaches can build in-country capacity and reduce reliance on international consultants. Alternative supervision models, such as peer or group supervision, or the creation of global communities of practice, should also be explored to maintain fidelity while keeping costs manageable.
- **Strengthen community partnerships and support co-produced scale-up models.** Successful CBITS implementation consistently depends on strong engagement with school leadership and community actors. Future investments should support models of delivery that embed co-production into design, implementation, and evaluation phases. This includes documenting best practices for stakeholder engagement and providing advocacy tools—such as data dashboards and case studies—that can be used by school leaders and policymakers to justify and expand CBITS adoption.

Key references:

- Goodkind, J. R., LaNoue, M. D., & Milford, J. (2010). Adaptation and implementation of cognitive behavioural intervention for trauma in schools with American Indian youth. *Journal of Clinical Child & Adolescent Psychology*, 39(6), 858-872
- Grande AJ, Hoffmann MS, Evans-Lacko S, Ziebold C, de Miranda CT, Mcdaid D, Tomasi C and Ribeiro WS (2023) Efficacy of school-based interventions for mental health problems in children and adolescents in low and middle-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front. Psychiatry* 13:1012257. doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2022.1012257
- Jaycox LH, Cohen JA, Mannarino AP, Walker DW, Langley AK, Gegenheimer KL, Scott M, Schonlau M. Children's mental health care following Hurricane Katrina: a field trial of trauma-focused psychotherapies. *J Trauma Stress*. 2010 Apr;23(2):223-31. doi: 10.1002/jts.20518. PMID: 20419730; PMCID: PMC2860874.
- Jaycox L, Langley A, Hoover S (2018) *Cognitive Behavioural Intervention for Trauma in Schools*. Second edition. Rand Corporation, Santa Monica, California. Available here: <http://www.cbitsprogram.org/>
- Kataoka SH, Stein BD, Jaycox LH, Wong M, Escudero P, Tu W, Zaragoza C, Fink A. A school-based mental health programme for traumatized Latino immigrant children. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 2003 Mar;42(3):311-8. doi: 10.1097/00004583-200303000-00011. PMID: 12595784.
- Kataoka S, Jaycox LH, Wong M, Nadeem E, Langley A, Tang L, Stein BD. Effects on school outcomes in low-income minority youth: preliminary findings from a community-partnered study of a school-based trauma intervention. *Ethn Dis*. 2011 Summer;21(3 Suppl 1):S1-71-7. PMID: 22352083; PMCID: PMC3287975.
- Langley, A. and Jaycox, L. (2024) *The Bounce Back: An Elementary School Intervention for Childhood Trauma (Bounce Back): At-A-Glance*. Los Angeles, CA & Durham, NC: National Center for Child Traumatic Stress.
- Morsette, A., Swaney, G., Stolle, D., Schuldberg, D., van den Pol, R., & Young, M. (2009). Cognitive behavioral intervention for trauma in schools (CBITS): School-based treatment on a rural American Indian reservation. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 40(1), 169-178.
- Nadeem E, Jaycox LH, Kataoka SH, Langley AK, Stein BD. Going to Scale: Experiences Implementing a School-Based Trauma Intervention. *School Psych Rev*. 2011 Dec;40(4):549-568. PMID: 27346911; PMCID: PMC4917015.
- Pfeiffer E, Dörrie L, Köksal J, Krech F, Muche R, Segler J, Sachser C. Evaluation of "Cognitive Behavioral Intervention for Trauma in Schools" (CBITS) in child welfare programs in Germany: study protocol of a randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2024 Jun 19;25(1):399. doi: 10.1186/s13063-024-08190-x. PMID: 38898537; PMCID: PMC11186087.
- Stein, B.D., Jaycox, L.H., Kataoka, S.H., Wong, M., Langley, A.K., Avila, J.L., Bonilla, A., Castillo-Campos, P., Cohen, J.B., Dean, K.L., DuClos, J.L., Elliott, M.N., Escudero, P., Fink, A., Fuentes, S., Gegenheimer, K.L., Halsey, K., Mannarino, A.P., Nadeem, E., Ngo, V.K., O'Donoghue, V.P., Schonlau, M., Scott, M.M., Sharma, P., Tu, W., Walker, D., & Zaragoza, C. *Helping Children Cope with Violence and Trauma: A School-Based Programme That Works*. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation, 2011. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_briefs/RB4557-2.html.
- Thomas FC, Puente-Duran S, Mutschler C, Monson CM. Trauma-focused cognitive behavioral therapy for children and youth in low and middle-income countries: A systematic review. *Child Adolesc Ment Health*. 2022 May;27(2):146-160. doi: 10.1111/camh.12435. Epub 2020 Nov 20. PMID: 33216426.
- World Health Organization (2023) *Mental Health Gap Action Programme (mhGAP) guideline for mental, neurological and substance use disorders*. Geneva. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

EXERCISE AND THERAPY

Pipeline stage: Improve and test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Professor, School of Psychiatry, University in Australia
- Associate Professor, School of Psychology, University in Australia

Target disorders:

Physical activity or exercise is recommended both as a stand-alone treatment and as a supportive adjunct (alongside cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), mindfulness-based interventions, and psychotherapy) for the treatment of depression, anxiety, and PTSD; applicability to psychosis is also high, particularly when considering early intervention for first episode psychosis.

Overview of intervention:

There are two main approaches that must be distinguished when considering combined exercise and therapy interventions:

- Integrated Approach: Elements of both physical activity and psychological therapy are blended into a single programme that incorporates key active ingredients from each intervention type (e.g. ClimbAid).
- Parallel Approach: Psychological and physical activity interventions are delivered separately but concurrently throughout the course of treatment.

The parallel approach is the most commonly implemented in practice. However, research on this remains limited, largely due to the high variability in combined interventions and the predominant focus of existing studies on evaluating the effects of physical activity alone.

Variability relates to the multiple combinations of both psychological and physical activity interventions that can be offered concurrently. Psychological interventions where exercise is commonly recommended as an adjunct include cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), mindfulness-based therapies, and psychotherapy. Physical activity interventions offered as adjuncts vary in several aspects. These include: the type and intensity of exercise (e.g., aerobic activities like running or dancing, anaerobic or resistance-based training such as strength exercises), the degree of mind-body integration (e.g., yoga or tai chi), and the mode (e.g., group classes or individualized coaching), setting (e.g. within health care facilities or gyms, community halls) and personnel involved in intervention delivery (trained exercise therapists compared to physical activity instructors or volunteers).

Most adjunct physical activity interventions are offered via structured programmes rather than self-directed activities (Kvam et al., 2015). These programmes are typically delivered in group formats, span multiple sessions, and last anywhere from 4–6 weeks to as long as 24 months, with most short-term programs concluding around the 12-week mark. While some programmes focus on a single type of exercise, this appears to be relatively uncommon, as multiple exercise modalities are often incorporated.

Scope:

This deep dive offers an overview of relevant evidence on combination exercise and therapy interventions, delivered either via integrated or parallel modalities as noted above. Where relevant, we will comment on physical activity as a standalone.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Physical activity can influence mental health through multiple mechanisms. Certain forms of exercise, such as yoga and tai chi, have long been associated with improved mental well-being. Today, these activities are recognised for their role in fostering the **mind-body connection**, which refers to the interplay between brain function, psychological state, bodily processes, and behaviour. The goal of such interventions is to enhance both mental and physical health by leveraging their reciprocal relationship (Guendelman et al., 2017; Rzeghi & Ouyang, 2020).

More broadly, research has identified two primary pathways through which physical activity impacts mental health: **biological** and **psychosocial**. The biological pathway includes neuromolecular changes that contribute to mental health improvements. For instance, physical activity has been shown to alleviate depression by increasing neurotrophic factor expression, enhancing serotonin and norepinephrine availability, regulating hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis activity, and reducing systemic inflammation (Singh, 2023).

Certain population groups may experience particularly strong benefits from physical activity interventions. For example, Szuhany (2024) highlights improvements in sleep as a key mechanism by which physical activity enhances mental health, noting that postpartum women, in particular, benefit from these effects. Beyond biological mechanisms, physical activity also influences **psychosocial factors**, such as fostering social connections and improving confidence in social interactions—especially through group-based activities like team sports.

Historically, research on physical activity and mental health primarily examined the impact of exercise as a standalone treatment for specific conditions. Early studies often focused on individuals with PTSD, as this population frequently required both **physical and psychological rehabilitation**. Consequently, some of the first combined exercise and therapy interventions emerged within this group. A key facilitator of intervention development in this regard was the broad focus of researchers and funders on supporting survivors of war and conflict; with a lot of early research focused on army veterans in particular.

As evidence of the mental health benefits of exercise grew, researchers began investigating whether physical activity could serve as a replacement for pharmacological or psychological treatments. Much of the existing research has focused on comparing physical activity alone to standard treatments. High levels of interest among physical rehabilitation researchers have served to advance the field. However, as findings increasingly suggest that physical activity is best suited as an adjunct rather than a replacement (including due to effects of physical activity on side-effects of pharmacological treatment as for first episode psychosis). There is growing interest in exploring combined exercise-therapy interventions. One key barrier that is holding back research in this area relates to the need for involvement of different disciplines, which has historically been difficult to do as mental health research has been dominated by psychological and psychiatric professions.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

There has been considerable interest in documenting the effects of physical activity on depression, anxiety and psychosis. Across this work, several trends seem to emerge, which are relevant to consider for combined interventions also.

First, physical activity appears to be an effective adjunct treatment for mental health, though the quality of existing evidence is often low to moderate. Singh et al (2023) conducted a large-scale review of 1,039 randomised controlled trials (RCTs) involving 128,119 participants, concluding that all types of physical activity have a moderate positive effect on depression (median effect size = -0.43) and anxiety (median effect size = -0.42). However, the review also highlighted significant methodological limitations across studies, such as a focus on participants with only moderate depression and assessments conducted immediately after intervention cessation, making long-term effects uncertain. Additionally, most systematic reviews in this space (77 of 97) were rated as low-quality, raising concerns about the reliability of conclusions.

These findings align with earlier research on depression and anxiety. Kvam et al. (2015), analysing 23 RCTs (977 participants), found that physical activity had a moderate to large effect on depressive symptoms when compared to usual care. However, when compared directly to psychological or pharmacological treatments, its effects were minimal and statistically insignificant. Similar results were reported in studies focused on anxiety by Stonerock et al. (2015, 12 RCTs) and an updated review in 2024 (25 RCTs). The latter review included studies from five continents but found that most were small (median participant number = 56), highly variable in exercise type, and lacked long-term follow-up. Only 2 out of 13 studies in individuals with anxiety showed clear benefits of physical activity.

For PTSD, Jadhakan et al. (2022) and Rosenbaum et al. (2015a) reported that while exercise programmes can be beneficial, evidence quality remains a concern. Similarly, research on psychosis suggests potential benefits, but findings are inconsistent. Brokmeier et al. (2020) examined longitudinal data to explore whether physical activity could reduce psychosis onset. While initial results suggested a protective effect, this association disappeared when confounding factors were accounted for. Shannon et al. (2020) focused on first-episode psychosis and exercise; the authors found only five relevant studies, two of which also measured psychotic symptom severity. These studies reported symptom reductions among participants who engaged in structured exercise programs.

Second, the impact of physical activity interventions differs across populations. Singh et al. (2023) identified greater benefits for individuals with chronic illnesses and postpartum women. Similarly, Jadhakan et al. (2022) and Rosenbaum et al. (2015a) explored the link between PTSD and cardiovascular disease, emphasizing that physical activity may be particularly beneficial for those with chronic health conditions. However, both reviews highlighted a major challenge: many studies lack sufficient data to differentiate effects by population group or exercise type. Few studies incorporate anthropometric measurements, limiting the ability to analyse the interaction between physical and mental health.

Third, the effectiveness of physical activity interventions seems to depend on factors such as intensity, duration, and exercise type. Singh et al. (2023) found that shorter, high-intensity programs (under 12 weeks) produced the most substantial effects. Jadhakan et al. (2022) reported that while most exercise types benefit PTSD treatment, resistance training alone showed no significant impact. The strongest evidence supports multimodal programs that combine cardiovascular and resistance training. In contrast, Shannon et al. (2020) identified yoga as the most effective intervention for psychosis, though they rated the overall evidence quality as low to moderate.

While research on combined physical activity and psychological or pharmacological treatments remains limited, emerging evidence in this space suggests promising results and supports general. Noetel et al. (2024) conducted a network meta-analysis examining the effects of various interventions, including combinations of exercise with therapy or medication, on depression. They found that aerobic exercise combined with therapy was as effective as exercise combined with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), and both approaches had similar effects to cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) alone. The study

also reinforced broader trends observed in the literature: exercise effectiveness correlated with intensity, and different groups responded differently to combined interventions. Notably, men showed greater benefits from yoga, tai chi, and aerobic exercise when paired with psychotherapy. Additionally, yoga and aerobic exercise combined with psychotherapy appeared more effective for older adults than for younger individuals.

In contrast, the Galenos review of PTSD specifically presents mixed results in relation to combination exercise and therapy. One challenge for the Galenos review relates to how it differentiates between combined vs. single interventions and groups studies for further synthesis. For example, the review compares 'exercise and treatment as usual' to treatment as usual, where treatment as usual in one case involves psychotherapy; in this case the combination version seems to be more effective. In other cases, 'exercise and therapy' are compared to other types of combination interventions (e.g. attention control and therapy); in these cases, results are mixed. Overall risk of bias across literature appears high.

Research Gaps

- **Limited focus on combined interventions with challenges in synthesis:** Most research still aims to demonstrate the benefits of physical activity (PA) alone, rather than its combined effect with psychological therapy. There is clear emerging interest in combined interventions, but uncertainty remains regarding how they should be studied. Key questions include whether PA should be examined as a prescribed intervention as part of a parallel modality or as part of a genuinely integrated therapeutic approach. For synthesis, it is particularly important to identify a common taxonomy for how interventions should be treated and grouped, i.e. it is important to find clinically relevant ways of grouping and describing studies, rather than relying on author descriptions.
- **More robust, large-scale research with opportunity for exploring mechanisms of action in diverse groups:** Many existing studies lack blinding and rigorous methodologies, reducing confidence in findings. More well-controlled and large-scale trials (or longitudinal studies) are needed, particularly those targeting specific mental health populations and studying diverse combination interventions. Trials must also be clearer on the mechanisms tested and offer opportunity for investigation of diverse mediators (e.g. social interaction, mindfulness, increased self-efficacy, neurobiological changes). Data collected should also allow for disaggregation, particularly by age, gender, disability and/or presence of another comorbidity. The intersection of non-communicable or long-term diseases such as cardiovascular disease or HIV, and mental health conditions, remains under-researched.

Relevance to PLE:

There seems to be a general lack of PLE involvement in relation to exercise and therapy interventions, with intervention development primarily relying on interested physical therapists and/or psychologists active in this space. PLE opinions are primarily sought during improvement and testing of interventions or later on during adoption once interventions are available, for example to identify preferred formats (e.g. group or individual based) for specific individuals.

However, when asked, PLE note that exercise and therapy is highly relevant to communities, explicitly also noting that exercise is an entry point for offering therapy "*There is also a sort of greater acceptance of these (exercise and art) and also implementation hence also becomes more connected to people's emotions and also their needs, actually what the community needs in that sense.*" One PLE respondent further noted that there are immediate benefits of combining exercise and therapy "*I have noted that over time, the more I combine the two, the better I am even in handling very small issues or any other issue that arises.*" Another respondent went on to say "*But movement helped me to reconnect with my body and*

my inner being. And that was my experience with exercising and the people around me have also seen the positive side of exercising while suffering through this kind of mental illness or any other emotional distress.”

The HeAL statement is unique in setting out the expectations of PLE of psychosis, specifically young people. The statement originated from an international working group iphYs (international physical health in youth stream), which evolved from the International Early Psychosis Association conference in Amsterdam (2010). Investment in concerted efforts to bring specific groups together to identify expectations of interventions and also discuss lived experience can thus be seen as a facilitator for further influence (the HeAL statement is since frequently quoted across research specifically).

Across the evidence, yoga and walking are most frequently identified as accepted and preferred interventions. However, study authors note that acceptability is under-researched, and that some exercise modalities are rarely offered/ promoted among specific groups (e.g. tai chi among younger populations is rarely studied). Both the HeAL statement and published literature note other types of barriers that PLE encounter, including language proficiency to engage with physical activity, prohibitive costs for accessing physical activity (e.g. when needing to use gyms) as well as lack of physical activity adaptation to cultural backgrounds, ability or prior trauma. In relation to the latter, the predominant delivery of physical activity programmes in gyms or exercise halls, where men and/or loud noises dominate are particularly noted affect uptake of services and continued engagement.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Czosnek et al (2019) carried out an umbrella review to identify health benefits, costs and safety of physical activity programmes for mental health conditions. The authors found no cost data that could speak to physical activity interventions. Indeed, prior research on this topic by Park and colleagues (2013) identified only three relevant studies among persons with the mental health conditions of interest. Findings were mixed:

- A Spanish study focused on supervised walking found this to be highly cost-effective (\$449 (€311, 2005 prices) per QALY gained, 99% probability of being cost effective for national threshold),
- A Welsh study on the National Exercise Referral Scheme noted a cost-effective intervention (\$46,150 (£30,000, 2009 prices) per QALY gained, 89% probability of being cost effective for national threshold),
- A small English study focused on facilitated physical activity found that there was no impact on clinical depression outcomes, however, there was evidence of sustained physical activity at 12 month follow up which could have benefits for other long-term conditions if sustained.

Lack of evidence on cost-effectiveness and costs of combined intervention delivery were noted to affect scaling and adoption. Interviewees noted that national health systems are usually expected to facilitate physical activity access (including cost coverage) for those in need, but lack of appropriate cost and outcome data makes it difficult to build an investment case. Importantly, comparative evidence is needed here, including on the potential for combined exercise and therapy interventions to affect pharmacological product use; the latter is highly linked not just to costs of care but also healthcare associated carbon footprint so should be minimised.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Most evidence in this field comes from high-income countries and is primarily applicable to those settings. Its relevance to low-resource environments is uncertain, as these areas often have different physical activity preferences and infrastructure. For example, many countries face extreme heat, flooding, or limited

access to green spaces and outdoor gyms. Additionally, cultural norms may influence where and how different groups, such as women and men, engage in physical activity.

Scalability presents challenges even in high-income settings. Czosnek (2022) examined implementation in Australia, identifying barriers and proposing a logic model for intervention. Studies, including Lederman (2017), highlight the importance of:

- Establishing and continuously refining multidisciplinary approaches (e.g., determining which healthcare or support professionals should be involved, offsetting the costs of combined interventions, and integrating monitoring and evaluation, including digital tools).
- Shifting community perspectives—including caregivers and researchers—toward recovery rather than just symptom reduction.
- Embedding behaviour change strategies that foster competence, autonomy, and relatedness for long-term impact.

Physical activity can be effectively integrated into chronic disease programs and various other sectors (e.g., education, security), offering multiple entry points. However, evidence on the effectiveness of online-facilitated programs remains mixed (Rosenbaum et al (2015b).

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

There are considerable challenges with integrated exercise and therapy interventions if access is restricted only to those who can pay. The intervention thus has potential to increase inequities. Similarly, interviewees noted that intervention participants may have varying abilities to participate in physical exercise; however, it was noted that qualified physical therapists should be able to adjust exercise intensity, duration and type based on ability levels and preferences. Barriers to access are also high in low-resource settings without relevant infrastructure; e.g. in low-resource settings there are few public resources (e.g. cycle paths, public walkways, public gyms) that can be accessed at low cost.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Most of the research to date has focused on examining whether exercise can affect mental health outcomes. Most research and expertise in promoting physical activity originates in high-income countries, with limited evidence on applicability of approaches, or their effectiveness, in low-income contexts. There is high potential for offering low-cost physical activity interventions alongside simple therapeutic interventions in low-resource settings, however this remains a significant gap in research. Interviewees also noted a lack of research on how best to scale interventions, e.g. via "train-the-trainer" approaches that may accept minor reductions in fidelity in exchange for substantial increases in scope and cost-effectiveness.

Lack of champions which can push forward a research agenda in this space is notable. Further, discordant professional views on both research and treatment approaches is evident across the field. Interviewees noted that among health and care professionals themselves it is contentious to speak of combined interventions, with psychologists and psychiatrists doubting the relevance of offering physical exercise. One important issue in this regard seems to be the lack of a dose-response relationship; evidence largely suggests that combined exercise and therapy interventions result in similar benefits to those secured via pharmacological or psychological management alone. Researchers and clinicians, however, have noted that they expect to see clear benefits of exercise and therapy before recommending it to patients. Lack of knowledge among professionals – as well as lack of evidence on additional physical health benefits and costs of care averted – are considerable barriers to overcome to shift opinion.

Further, stakeholders in consultations mentioned that communities themselves may have doubts over whether physical exercise can contribute to alleviating mental health symptoms. However, some stakeholders identified that it may be less stigmatising to access exercise and therapy services, compared to psychological or pharmacological treatment.

Recommendations for investment:

Based on the above, specific recommendations to advance scale up and adoption of combined exercise and therapy emerge.

Research Recommendations

- **Establishing expert consensus** on how interventions and comparators or controls in this space should be grouped for further synthesis and assessment – this would facilitate reviews like Galenos and others. Relevant comparators include common psychological interventions (e.g. CBT, psychotherapy and mindfulness-based interventions). However, studies should also consider comparisons with combination interventions (therapy and pharmacological) or pharmacological interventions alone. Controls in contrast include no treatment or waitlist controls.
- **Increase the number of rigorous, large-scale trials** that put in place blinding and are conducted in populations with moderate to severe depression and anxiety, as well as diverse populations affected by psychosis. Studies in low-resource settings, where additional implementation challenges are considered, are of absolute priority.
- **Embed cost and cost-effectiveness analyses into trials**, to help consider a case for investment in relation to combined interventions. In this regard, it is key to consider also long-term benefits of combined interventions. Studies should also evaluate impacts on reducing reliance on pharmacological treatments and assess broader benefits. These may include reduced demand for pharmaceutical and reduced overall costs of care, but also reduced carbon footprint from manufacturing of pharmaceuticals.
- **Investing in lived experience involvement and leadership** of this space via targeted PLE meetings and/or initiatives like HeAL would be beneficial in guiding research in the space.
- **Investment in developing and encouraging research and practice champions**, which can set and pursue a research and/or advocacy agenda in this space would be hugely beneficial. These champions could encourage collaboration across fields like physical therapy, psychology, and psychiatry to harmonise approaches.

Key references:

- Brokmeier, L. L., Firth, J., Vancampfort, D., Smith, L., Deenik, J., Rosenbaum, S., Stubbs, B., & Schuch, F. B. (2020). Does physical activity reduce the risk of psychosis? A systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective studies. *Psychiatry Research*, 284, 112675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2019.112675>
- Czosnek, L., Lederman, O., Cormie, P., Zopf, E., Stubbs, B., & Rosenbaum, S. (2019). Health benefits, safety and cost of physical activity interventions for mental health conditions: A meta-review to inform translation efforts. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 16, 140–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2018.11.001>
- Czosnek, L., Rosenbaum, S., Rankin, N. M., Zopf, E. M., Cormie, P., Herbert, B., & Richards, J. (2023). Implementation of physical activity interventions in a community-based youth mental healthcare service: A case study of context, strategies, and outcomes. *Early Intervention in Psychiatry*, 17(2), 212–222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eip.13324>
- International Physical Health in Youth (iphYs) Working Group. (2013). *Healthy Active Lives (HeAL) consensus statement*. <https://www.iphys.org.au/heal-consensus-statement>

- Jadhakhan, F., Lambert, N., Middlebrook, N., Evans, D. W., & Falla, D. (2022). Is exercise/physical activity effective at reducing symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder in adults—A systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *13*, 943479. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.943479>
- Kvam, S., Kleppe, C. L., Nordhus, I. H., & Hovland, A. (2016). Exercise as a treatment for depression: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, *202*, 67–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2016.03.063>
- Lederman, O., Suetani, S., Stanton, R., Chapman, J., Korman, N., Rosenbaum, S., Ward, P. B., & Siskind, D. (2017). Embedding exercise interventions as routine mental health care: Implementation strategies in residential, inpatient and community settings. *Australasian Psychiatry*, *25*(5), 451–455. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1039856217711054>
- Noetel, M., Sanders, T., Gallardo-Gómez, D., Taylor, P., Del Pozo Cruz, B., Van Den Hoek, D., Smith, J. J., Mahoney, J., Spathis, J., Moresi, M., Pagano, R., Pagano, L., Vasconcellos, R., Arnott, H., Varley, B., Parker, P., Biddle, S., & Lonsdale, C. (2024). Effect of exercise for depression: Systematic review and network meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *BMJ*, e075847. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2023-075847>
- Park, A.-L., McDaid, D., Weiser, P., Von Gottberg, C., Becker, T., Kilian, R. & for the HELPS Network. (2013). Examining the cost effectiveness of interventions to promote the physical health of people with mental health problems: A systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, *13*(1), 787. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-787>
- Rosenbaum, S., Vancampfort, D., Steel, Z., Newby, J., Ward, P. B., & Stubbs, B. (2015a). Physical activity in the treatment of Post-traumatic stress disorder: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychiatry Research*, *230*(2), 130–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2015.10.017>
- Rosenbaum, S., Newby, J. M., Steel, Z., Andrews, G., & Ward, P. B. (2015b). Online physical activity interventions for mental disorders: A systematic review. *Internet Interventions*, *2*(2), 214–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.invent.2015.04.001>
- Shannon, A., McGuire, D., Brown, E., & O'Donoghue, B. (2020). A systematic review of the effectiveness of group-based exercise interventions for individuals with first episode psychosis. *Psychiatry Research*, *293*, 113402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113402>
- Singh, B., Olds, T., Curtis, R., Dumuid, D., Virgara, R., Watson, A., Szeto, K., O'Connor, E., Ferguson, T., Eglitis, E., Miatke, A., Simpson, C. E., & Maher, C. (2023). Effectiveness of physical activity interventions for improving depression, anxiety and distress: An overview of systematic reviews. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, *57*(18), 1203–1209. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2022-106195>
- Stonerock, G. L., Hoffman, B. M., Smith, P. J., & Blumenthal, J. A. (2015). Exercise as Treatment for Anxiety: Systematic Review and Analysis. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, *49*(4), 542–556. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-014-9685-9>
- Szuhany, K. L., Sullivan, A. J., Gills, J. L., & Kredlow, M. A. (2024). The impact of exercise interventions on sleep in adult populations with depression, anxiety, or posttraumatic stress: Review of the current evidence and future directions. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10865-024-00532-z>

FAMILY THERAPY

Pipeline stage: Improve and test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Marriage and family therapist and qualitative researcher.
- Trainer, researcher, book author and Professor at a University in the USA.

Target disorders:

Family therapy demonstrates efficacy across a spectrum of mental health conditions, with systematic reviews supporting its application for schizophrenia, depressive and anxiety disorders, and conduct-related challenges (Carr, 2024; Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018; Varghese *et al.*, 2020). For schizophrenia, meta-analyses highlight its role in reducing relapse rates by moderating high expressed emotion (EE) environments and improving caregiver coping (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). In depression and anxiety, systematic reviews underscore its equivalence to individual CBT for symptom reduction, with added benefits in relational resilience and perinatal contexts (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018; Vossler *et al.*, 2024). Emerging evidence also supports its use for youth conduct problems, though further reviews are needed to clarify its effectiveness for personality disorders (Carr, 2024).

Overview of intervention:

Family therapy is a *systemic* form of psychotherapy designed to reduce distress and conflict by targeting relational dynamics and behavioural patterns within family systems. Rather than relying on a strictly linear model, this modality operates within a *circular framework* that acknowledges how family members' emotions and behaviours mutually influence one another (Varghese *et al.*, 2020). Owing to its emphasis on relational patterns and collaborative problem-solving, family therapy can be applied across various levels of care - from outpatient and community-based programs to inpatient or residential settings - and can be adapted to low-resource contexts when adequately supported with training, supervision, and organisational infrastructure (Bucci *et al.*, 2016), (Negash *et al.*, 2022).

Because it encompasses *multiple theoretical orientations*, family therapy is better understood as an overarching category of interventions rather than a single, uniform approach. Psychoeducational family therapy, for instance, has demonstrated efficacy in preventing relapse among individuals with severe mental conditions like schizophrenia through enhanced coping strategies and illness understanding (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). Systemic models typically emphasise restructuring dysfunctional interaction patterns, deploying techniques such as problem-solving and communication training (Varghese *et al.*, 2020). Attachment-based family therapy focuses on repairing ruptured bonds - especially effective in adolescent depression - while meta-analyses link it to a reduction in suicidal ideation relative to individual CBT (Aswegen *et al.*, 2023). Meanwhile, cognitive-behavioural family therapy integrates psychoeducation, cognitive restructuring, and problem-solving to address relational factors in contexts such as perinatal depression (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018). Collectively, these approaches demonstrate family therapy's adaptability for both preventive interventions and long-term management of chronic conditions, marking it as a valuable, systemically oriented option within diverse cultural contexts.

Scope:

Cognitive-Behavioural Family Therapy (CB-FT) and Psychoeducational Family Therapy stand out as two of the most empirically supported approaches for addressing anxiety, depression, and psychosis

(particularly schizophrenia). Given their strong evidence base, this deep dive focuses on these two approaches to examine their mechanisms of action, common implementation challenges, and potential for wider scale-up in diverse settings. Research underscores the importance of tailoring these models to particular cultural and resource contexts – particularly in low-income regions and marginalised communities – highlighting the need for ongoing adaptation and capacity-building to achieve optimal outcomes for individuals and families living with depression, anxiety, or psychosis.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Family therapy in the United States emerged after World War II, initially informed by psychoanalytic influences and gradually shifting its focus toward environmental factors in the aetiology of severe mental health conditions. Early theoretical work posited that dysfunctional family environments and unclear communication patterns could contribute to disorders such as schizophrenia. Traditional systemic family therapy therefore, gained traction in the 1960s and 1970s, although many of its underlying concepts were not yet substantiated by empirical research. Subsequent investigations have not established a causal link between distorted family interactions and schizophrenia but have highlighted the importance of family involvement in recovery processes (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). In the 1980s, growing recognition of families' roles in treatment prompted the development of interventions such as “Family Management,” “Psychoeducational Family Treatment,” or “Family Care,” which emphasise education about mental illness, early-warning sign monitoring, and the mitigation of high expressed emotion (EE). Landmark outcome studies during this period reported a notable decline in relapse rates when these interventions were employed (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023).

Psychoeducational Family Therapy subsequently emerged as a key approach, often rooted in stress–vulnerability or bio–psycho–social models of psychosis (Salaminiou *et al*, 2015). Such interventions aim to reduce family-based stressors - particularly criticism, stigma, and negative communication patterns - while enhancing skills in problem-solving, crisis management, and service access. Sessions typically extend over several weeks, using methods such as modelling, rehearsal, and feedback to solidify behavioural changes.

Cognitive-Behavioural Family Therapy (CB-FT) similarly targets recurring interaction patterns but places additional emphasis on modifying unhelpful beliefs at the family-system level, drawing from cognitive-behavioural frameworks. Meanwhile, family systems theory continues to inform these models by examining the roles, rules, and boundaries that shape intrafamilial functioning (Aswegen *et al.*, 2023). Overall, the theory of change underlying both psychoeducational and CB-FT approaches posits that building shared understanding, increasing supportive communication, and adopting skills-based interventions can reduce relapse risk and alleviate distress for individuals with severe mental health challenges and their families.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Family therapy encompasses a range of approaches, with Cognitive-Behavioural Family Therapy (CB-FT) and Psychoeducational Family Therapy being widely researched for their application across mental health conditions. Both modalities demonstrate empirical support for improving outcomes in schizophrenia, depression, anxiety, and perinatal mental health, though their mechanisms and implementation contexts differ.

Depression and Anxiety

Cognitive-Behavioural Family Therapy (CB-FT) has shown consistent efficacy in reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety, particularly in adolescent and perinatal populations. Aswegen *et al.* (2023) examined 12 studies of family-based therapy for children and adolescents (ages 3-18) in the US, Europe,

and Australia – 7 included adolescents only (12-18), 2 included children (3-7), and 3 covered children to early adolescents (7-15). They emphasised CB-FT's capacity to engage caregivers in collaborative problem-solving, fostering relational resilience alongside symptom reduction. The overall effect size for treatment versus active control has been found to be $g = 0.22$ (95% confidence interval [CI]: $-0.05-0.50$), and for treatment versus non-active control to be $g = 0.46$ (95% CI: $-0.09-1.01$). In perinatal contexts, CB-FT's focus on communication and role transitions has been linked to improved maternal mental health outcomes (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018). In that meta-analysis by Cluxton-Keller & Bruce (2018), seven studies were included ($n = 801$ mothers and partners; 385 in control, 416 in intervention), predominantly white (91%), middle-class, with at least a high school education.

Psychoeducational Family Therapy has demonstrated sustained symptom reduction for depression, particularly in long-term care (Katsuki et al., 2022) through its focus on family education and crisis management. Katsuki et al. (2022) included five studies ($n = 301$) involving patients with major depressive disorder (MDD) plus one family member—175 in intervention and 126 in control—from Belgium, Finland, India, Japan (2), the USA (2), China, and Italy. Adaptations for perinatal populations highlight its utility in reducing stigma and improving communication, though implementation variability underscores the need for standardised protocols (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018).

Psychosis

For schizophrenia, CB-FT shows promise in mitigating high expressed emotion (EE) environments, though its role as an adjunct to pharmacotherapy requires further validation (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023).

Psychoeducational Family Therapy is particularly effective in schizophrenia management, where its structured, phased format reduces relapse rates by enhancing caregiver coping strategies and reducing criticism (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). Compared to standard care, family intervention notably decreased total symptom severity (0.36/0.30), relapse rates (0.55/0.62), hospital admissions (0.53/0.46), and improved social functioning (0.22/0.38) both during treatment and throughout a one-year follow-up. Longer treatment durations resulted in higher effect sizes (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023).

When compared, CB-FT and Psychoeducational Family Therapy offer complementary strengths. CB-FT excels in enhancing relational functioning through cognitive-behavioural techniques, while psychoeducational approaches prioritize systemic education and caregiver support. Combined approaches integrating psychoeducational elements into CB-FT have been explored in schizophrenia and perinatal depression, though evidence for their scalability remains limited (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023; Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018).

Key challenges include the need for cultural adaptations beyond Western contexts and longitudinal studies to assess sustained outcomes. Research by Negash et al. (2022) highlights mismatches between Eurocentric therapeutic norms and family structures in marginalised communities, while existing trials often lack long-term follow-up data to assess sustained relapse prevention (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023).

Relevance to PLE:

Systematic reviews emphasise the importance of co-designing interventions with families affected by mental health conditions to enhance relevance and engagement, particularly in marginalised communities where stigma and structural barriers disproportionately limit access (Negash et al., 2022). For example, perinatal family therapy models developed in partnership with mothers demonstrate improved retention and satisfaction by addressing gendered role expectations and intergenerational caregiving dynamics (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018).

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Family therapy interventions, particularly Psychoeducational Family Therapy and Cognitive-Behavioural Family Therapy (CB-FT), require structured training, supervision, and organisational support to ensure fidelity. Psychoeducational programs for schizophrenia, for instance, typically involve 9–12 months of sessions with phased intensity, necessitating investments in clinician training, caregiver engagement, and systemic coordination (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). Task-sharing models have reduced costs in low-resource settings, though scalability depends on sustained supervision and cultural adaptation. Barriers such as staff shortages, competing clinical priorities, and underfunding often limit implementation, particularly in public health systems.

Cost-effectiveness analyses highlight family therapy's potential to reduce long-term healthcare expenditures. For schizophrenia, psychoeducational interventions lower relapse rates and hospital admissions, offsetting upfront training costs (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). In perinatal depression, family therapy models reduce maternal morbidity and associated child developmental costs, though evidence for low-income regions remains limited (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018). Digital delivery (e.g., telehealth, psychoeducational modules) offers promise for cost reduction but requires infrastructure investments (Carr, 2024).

Context, applicability and scalability:

Similarly to individual psychotherapy, though, family therapy is generally rooted in Eurocentric and Western views and practices, which are not always adequate for certain population groups, and many therapists do not recognise how cultural contexts influence how families establish themselves. Some studies highlight that the lack of culturally sensitive practices and of respect and equal partnership between clinicians and families are important barriers to implement interventions and point out the need for further research that include the adaptation and implementation of family therapy interventions for minority groups (Negash *et al*, 2022). An interviewee corroborated this information by stating that CBT is traditionally Western driven and very directive, which will not be effective for everybody.

According to the interviewee, family therapy is very adaptable, but the research base is still very 'western' and practitioners often disagree on how the families should be defined (ie. how many individuals should they include, or which members should be considered as family). The interviewee suggested the need for flexibility in terms of the professionals to be trained to deliver family therapy interventions, as it is useful to have a healthcare background, but, in some contexts, it may be more helpful to have other professionals who care for families trained as well, such as teachers.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

Family therapy's potential to reduce mental health disparities is hindered by systemic inequities in access and cultural relevance. Marginalised populations - including racial/ethnic minorities, low-income families, and those in conflict-affected regions - face structural barriers such as cost, geographic scarcity of providers, and stigma (Negash *et al.*, 2022). Eurocentric therapeutic norms, such as prioritising nuclear family structures or individualism, often alienate communities with collectivist values or extended kinship networks, risking misalignment with local caregiving practices. Post-incarceration families, for example, may distrust institutionalised care or prioritise survival needs (e.g., housing) over therapy, underscoring the need for interventions that address socioeconomic contexts (Negash *et al.*, 2022).

Equitable implementation requires workforce diversification and culturally grounded adaptations. Task-sharing to train non-specialists (e.g., community health workers) could improve access in low-resource settings, while co-designing interventions with persons with lived experience (PLE) ensures cultural

responsiveness, as demonstrated in perinatal models (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018). However, systemic biases favouring biological treatments over relational approaches persist, sidelining family therapy in policy agendas and perpetuating inequities in communities where relational care may be more culturally resonant (Bucci et al., 2016).

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

- Some studies noted barriers to implementing family therapy interventions (FTIs) related to the skills and attitudes of the professionals delivering the interventions, such as insufficient training in FTIs (both on specific therapeutic skills, moving from individual to a more systemic model, and on the integration of family therapy into routine clinical practice), inadequate access to supervision, professionals experiencing more conflict in delivering this therapy in comparison with other types and lacking the confidence to deliver it, and a frequently observed preference for biological models for understanding mental disorders with a view of FTIs as an extra resource, but not the main one (Bucci *et al*, 2016).
- Other identified barriers are organisational and include limited staff finance and resources committed to FTIs when conflicting demands emerge, and insufficient support and service structure provided by managers to meet the objectives of FTIs (Bucci *et al*, 2016). Some studies observed that oftentimes if the organisational culture does not consider FTIs, they are not implemented, and that crisis interventions are frequently prioritised over FTIs (Bucci *et al*, 2016). Additional barriers are related to the service users and families, where negative attitudes from family members towards FTIs would impede them to participate in the therapy, or in cases where service users would be too overly medicated to take part in the interventions (Bucci *et al*, 2016).
- There are few high-quality studies that incorporate family therapeutic interventions into psychotherapeutic treatments for perinatal depression (Cluxton-Keller, Bruce, 2018), and authors highlight the need for more family therapy interventions across the phases of psychosis (Bucci *et al*, 2016). They inform that the duration and intensity of the interventions vary from trial to trial, so its optimal frequency is still not defined.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- **Build Evidence through Large-Scale Comparative Studies.** Donor investment in psychoeducational and cognitive-behavioural family therapy (CB-FT) is supported by meta-analyses demonstrating improved relapse prevention, symptom reduction, and caregiver well-being, particularly when these interventions are combined with pharmacotherapy for conditions such as schizophrenia and depression (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023). According to an interviewee, more research is needed, particularly in areas like bipolar disorder, drug use, and schizophrenia. They say that while there's already strong evidence that family therapy works, there's always room for more research, especially with diverse families around the world.
- **Prioritise Cost-Effectiveness Analyses.** While psychoeducational approaches for schizophrenia have been linked to a reduction in relapse and fewer hospital admissions (Hahlweg & Baucom, 2023), further economic evaluations are necessary to quantify broader impacts on healthcare expenditures and social costs. This includes examining indirect costs such as caregiver burden and workplace productivity losses. A clear articulation of return on investment can encourage policymakers to integrate family interventions into routine care, especially for high-burden conditions like schizophrenia,

depression, and anxiety. Research on perinatal depression also indicates the potential for targeted family therapy models to improve maternal–child outcomes and mitigate future healthcare costs (Cluxton-Keller & Bruce, 2018).

- **Support Implementation Research and Task-Sharing.** Task-sharing – training non-specialists (e.g., community health workers) under expert supervision - has facilitated the scale-up of psychosocial interventions in low-resource settings. Backing implementation studies that incorporate family therapy into primary care or community-based programs can illuminate factors such as processes, fidelity, and cultural adaptation. Moreover, partnerships with local health authorities, NGOs, and educational bodies can bolster the workforce pipeline, ensuring sustained delivery of family therapy approaches over time.

Ecosystems Recommendations

- **Explore Digital and Telehealth Delivery.** Recent evaluations suggest that online or telehealth formats hold promise for extending the reach of family therapy, particularly in regions with clinician shortages or geographic barriers (Carr, 2024). Although direct evidence on tele-family therapy remains limited, research into other remote psychosocial interventions reveals feasibility and acceptability across low-, middle-, and high-income contexts. Donor-funded pilot projects or randomised trials can determine whether digital psychoeducation modules or virtual CB-FT sessions preserve therapeutic efficacy, reduce costs, and foster greater family engagement. Such findings could then inform policy and programmatic decisions about digital mental health solutions.

Key References:

- Van Aswegen, T., Samartzi, E., Morris, L., van der Spek, N., de Vries, R., Seedat, S., & van Straten, A. (2023). Effectiveness of family-based therapy for depressive symptoms in children and adolescents: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Psychology*, 58(6), 499–511. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12926>
- Bucci, S., Berry, K., Barrowclough, C., & Haddock, G. (2016). Family intervention in psychosis. *Australian Psychologist*, 51(1), 62–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ap.12172>
- Carr, A. (2025). Family therapy and systemic interventions for child-focused problems: The evidence base. *Journal of Family Therapy*, 47, e12476. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6427.12476>
- Chen, Q., Zhao, W., Li, Q., & Sagi, H. (2021). The influence of family therapy on psychological stress and social adaptability of depressed patients. *WORK*, 69(2), 613–624. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-213503>
- Cluxton-Keller, F., & Bruce, M. L. (2018). Clinical effectiveness of family therapeutic interventions in the prevention and treatment of perinatal depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE*, 13(6), e0198730. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0198730>
- Hahlweg, K., & Baucom, D. Hahlweg, K., & Baucom, D. H. (2023). Family therapy for persons with schizophrenia: Neglected yet important. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*, 273(6), 819–824. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00406-022-01393-w>
- Katsuki, F., Watanabe, N., Yamada, A., & Hasegawa, T. (2022). Effectiveness of family psychoeducation for major depressive disorder: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BJPsych open*, 8(5), e148. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjo.2022.543>
- Negash, S., Chung, K., & Oh, S. (2022). Families post-release: Barriers and pathways to family therapy. *Family process*, 61(2), 609–624. <https://doi.org/10.1111/famp.12769>
- Salaminiou, E., Campbell, M., Simic, M., Kuipers, E., & Eisler, I. (2017). Intensive multi-family therapy for adolescent anorexia nervosa: An open study of 30 families. *Journal of Family Therapy*, 39(4), 498–513. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6427.12075>
- Varghese, M., Kirpekar, V., & Loganathan, S. (2020). Family Interventions: Basic Principles and Techniques. *Indian journal of psychiatry*, 62(Suppl 2), S192–S200. <https://doi.org/10.4103/psychiatry.IndianJPsychiatry.770.19>

SHAMIRI INTERVENTION PROGRAMME

Pipeline stage: Prototype exemplar

Stakeholders interviewed:

- A Founder and Scientific Director of Shamiri Institute
- Director of Service Delivery of Shamiri Institute

Target disorders:

The intervention specifically targets depression and anxiety symptoms among adolescents (in school settings) between 13-18 in low-resource settings.

Overview of intervention:

The Shamiri Intervention is a brief, group-based, lay-provider-delivered intervention designed to improve mental health outcomes among adolescents in low-resource settings. It focuses on building resilience, gratitude, and a growth mindset through simple, evidence-based psychological strategies. The intervention typically lasts 4 weeks, with weekly group sessions lasting about 1 hour each. The intervention was developed to target adolescents (ages 13-18) in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Kenya, where mental health resources are scarce. It is designed to be scalable and cost-effective, making it suitable for low-resource settings generally (Osborn et al., 2020).

The Shamiri Intervention consists of three core modules, delivered over four sessions:

1. Growth Mindset (two sessions): Teaches adolescents the concept that personal attributes and abilities can be developed through effort and perseverance.
2. Gratitude (one session): Encourages adolescents to recognise and appreciate positive aspects of their lives.
3. Value Affirmations (one session): Guides adolescents in identifying and affirming their core values, referred to as "virtues" within the intervention framework.

The programme is facilitated by trained lay providers—high school graduates aged 17 to 26—who complete a 10-hour training programme before leading group sessions of 8 to 15 adolescents. These sessions, conducted in school settings, incorporate reading activities, group discussions, and writing exercises to enhance engagement and learning (Osborn et al., 2020).

An interviewee explained that Shamiri trains older adolescents and young adults as lay providers for several key reasons. First, students often do not feel comfortable confiding in teachers, as they are typically seen as authority figures responsible for discipline and grading rather than as sources of personal support. Second, training this age group is logistically feasible in Kenya (and other African settings), where many young people take a gap year between high school and college to prepare for applications or explore other opportunities. This flexibility allows them to participate in the programme without making a long-term commitment. Finally, these lay providers serve as near-peer role models, making them more relatable and approachable for the students they support. By selecting this age group, Shamiri ensures that the intervention is both effective and practical for the communities it serves.

Scope:

We focus on the version of the intervention described above; this is the version currently available as an exemplar and undergoing additional work for improvement and testing.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The Shamiri Intervention is grounded in positive psychology and cognitive-behavioural principles. Its theory of change suggests that by promoting gratitude, a growth mindset, and resilience, adolescents can develop more effective coping mechanisms, alleviate symptoms of depression and anxiety, and enhance overall well-being (Osborn et al., 2019).

Rooted in the science of "character strength" interventions, the Shamiri Intervention targets positive psychological traits such as gratitude, a growth mindset, and value affirmation. These components are theorised to improve mental health by fostering resilience, reducing mental health stigma, and enhancing overall psychological well-being (Venturo-Conerly et al., 2021).

The intervention was developed through a multicultural collaboration between Kenyan and American experts, incorporating input from local stakeholders to ensure cultural relevance and contextual appropriateness. It is based on the premise that brief, non-pathologising interventions centered on positive psychological constructs—such as growth mindset, gratitude, and value affirmations—can improve mental health outcomes while reducing the stigma associated with seeking mental health care (Osborn et al., 2020). The intervention specifically targets adolescence because this is a key developmental stage where skills such as the ones envisioned can contribute to enhanced long-term social, educational and economic outcomes.

The intervention has gained support and popularity in Kenya given the above collaboration and also local stakeholder networks. However, further research in other settings is needed to advance the development of the intervention; this is a key barrier to further scaling.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The Shamiri Intervention is grounded in positive psychology and cognitive-behavioural principles. Its theory of change suggests that by promoting gratitude, a growth mindset, and resilience, adolescents can develop more effective coping mechanisms, alleviate symptoms of depression and anxiety, and enhance overall well-being (Osborn et al., 2019).

Rooted in the science of "character strength" interventions, the Shamiri Intervention targets positive psychological traits such as gratitude, a growth mindset, and value affirmation. These components are theorised to improve mental health by fostering resilience, reducing mental health stigma, and enhancing overall psychological well-being (Venturo-Conerly et al., 2021).

The intervention was developed through a multicultural collaboration between Kenyan and American experts, incorporating input from local stakeholders to ensure cultural relevance and contextual appropriateness. It is based on the premise that brief, non-pathologising interventions centered on positive psychological constructs—such as growth mindset, gratitude, and value affirmations—can improve mental health outcomes while reducing the stigma associated with seeking mental health care (Osborn et al., 2020).

The intervention has gained support and popularity in Kenya given the above collaboration and also local stakeholder networks. However, further research in other settings is needed to advance the development of the intervention; this is a key barrier to further scaling.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Evaluations have focused on both primary outcomes, such as depression and anxiety reduction, and secondary outcomes like social relationships, academic performance, and overall functioning. Given the strong academic pressures on students, the programme also assesses whether improved mental health leads to better academic performance. To date, studies were primarily randomised controlled trials involving Kenyan adolescents, consistently demonstrating substantial reductions in depression and anxiety symptoms, as well as improvements in academic performance and social support. Based on available evidence, there are no concerns that the intervention would cause harm. Important studies include:

- Osborn et al., 2019: In a randomised controlled trial conducted in Kenya, 28 participants who received the Shamiri Intervention exhibited greater improvements in mental health outcomes compared to 23 participants from a control group receiving standard care. Specifically, over a 4-week period (from baseline to 4-week follow-up post-intervention end), the intervention resulted in significant reductions in depression ($p = .038$, $d = .32$) and anxiety symptoms ($p = .039$, $d = .54$) relative to a study skills control group. Additionally, participants experienced enhanced academic performance ($p = .034$, $d = .32$) and reported higher levels of perceived social support from friends ($p = .028$, $d = .71$).
- Venturo-Conerly et al., 2021: This RCT had a sample size of 413 adolescents. Participants, aged 13 to 18 years from four secondary schools in Kenya, were assessed at baseline, post-treatment, and at two-week and seven-month follow-ups. The Shamiri intervention led to greater reductions in symptoms of depression and anxiety post-treatment extending to 7-month follow-up. Youths receiving Shamiri showed greater reductions in depressive symptoms at post treatment ($d = 0.35$) and at 7-month follow-up ($d = 0.45$) as well as greater reductions in anxiety symptoms at post treatment ($d = 0.37$) and 7-month follow-up ($d = 0.44$). Both the Shamiri intervention and a study skills control group reduced depression and anxiety symptoms; the low-cost Shamiri intervention had a greater effect, with effects lasting at least 7 months.
- Venturo-Conerly et al., 2024: This trial was done in Kenya with 1252 adolescents, the Shamiri intervention was evaluated alongside its individual components and a study-skills control group. Youths were evaluated at baseline, midpoint, endpoint, one-month, three-month and eight-month follow-up, a study-skills intervention demonstrated. Results show a notably larger effect size for depression ($d = 1.40$) and anxiety ($d = 1.68$). Similarly, the Shamiri intervention showed a slightly increased effect size in the current study (depression, $d = 1.33$; anxiety, $d = 1.71$). Youths across all conditions (growth, gratitude, values, combined Shamiri, and study-skills) experienced significant decreases in depression and anxiety symptoms and increases in well-being over time.

Gaps in research:

While randomised controlled trials as per the above have been conducted, early studies had small sample sizes, such as the 2018 trial with only 51 participants. Although later trials included larger samples, further research with even greater participant numbers is needed to ensure robust and generalizable findings. Interviewees spoke about diverse gaps in research. Among them, is understanding the moderators of effectiveness, specifically, identifying which populations benefit most from the intervention and who may require alternative approaches. Challenges in scaling research also pose a barrier, particularly due to logistical difficulties in data collection. Many participants complete assessments on paper rather than

digitally, making large-scale research more time-consuming and resource-intensive. Another major gap is the lack of comparative effectiveness research, as existing studies have not directly compared Shamiri to other mental health interventions to determine whether it performs better, worse, or similarly. Finally, adapting Shamiri to new contexts remains a significant challenge, as there is limited evidence on how to modify interventions for different populations without compromising effectiveness. Related to this, future research must also consider how to maintain intervention fidelity across contexts; variability could compromise effectiveness. Another significant challenge is securing funding for early-stage research, as global mental health funding tends to prioritise well-established interventions, leaving new programmes with limited financial support for development and initial testing. Addressing these gaps is essential for refining Shamiri, optimising its implementation, and expanding its impact in diverse settings.

Relevance to PLE:

The intervention was developed with input from local stakeholders to ensure cultural relevance and acceptability. It is delivered by lay providers, which reduces stigma and increases accessibility (Venturo-Conerly et al., 2021). This was reinforced by an interviewee who mentioned that one of its co-founders grew up in rural Kenya, attended local schools, and experienced the academic pressures faced by many Kenyan students. This personal background helped shape the intervention to be more relevant to young people in Kenya. Additionally, the first RCT was conducted in a Kenyan setting, ensuring that the intervention was tested within the local cultural and educational context.

Over time, the programme has been refined to remain culturally appropriate. However, it appears that engagement of people with lived experience of mental health was not a primary consideration in intervention development; rather the engagement developed over time.

According to one interviewee, the development team is intentionally composed primarily of individuals who are Kenyan and attended Kenyan high schools to ensure cultural relevance; while not youth themselves, the developers therefore drew on their own experiences. However, the interviewee noted that several team members identify as having lived experience with mental illness and contributed insights to the design of the intervention. The organisation also retains multiple individuals from the original development team who share this lived experience and have remained involved in the organisation over an extended period.

Furthermore, the team has continuously gathered feedback from nearly all participants in the intervention, with particular emphasis on input from the adolescent lay providers. This feedback has informed modifications and improvements to the intervention over time. One interviewee personally shared that, for them, understanding what works is based not only on academic and clinical training but also on personal experience on mental illness. They explained that having lived with mental illness, developing coping skills, and recognising which strategies are effective to then being able to help others.

While persons with lived experience have been engaged in Shamiri, this engagement could clearly be strengthened. Current engagement has ensured the intervention could be tested locally and reach prototyping stage. However, more equitable ways of engaging, specifically with young people with lived experience of mental health conditions, including in settings outside schools, or outside Kenya - is necessary for further adaptation improvement and testing.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Despite being labelled a low-cost intervention, Shamiri still requires essential materials and incurs specific costs which may be unsustainable for local education systems. It is delivered by lay providers (non-specialists) who receive brief training (10 hours), reducing the reliance on expensive mental health professionals and making it feasible for low-resource settings.

Base case cost assumptions estimated that delivering Shamiri costs \$15.17 (in 2021 U.S. dollars) per student. A sensitivity analysis estimated it cost between \$48.28 and \$172.72 to help one student in Shamiri achieve reliable and clinically significant change in depression and anxiety by 7-month follow-up. This cost-effectiveness is attributed to factors such as the use of lay providers, integration within an LMIC school setting, and a group-based format. At the 7-month follow-up, the cost per Number Needed to Treat (NNT) in Shamiri was between \$56.44 and \$172.72. For PHQ-8, at the 7-month follow-up, more students in Shamiri met the RCSC criteria for PHQ-8 change (43% vs. 29%), making the NNT 7.1 and the cost per NNT between \$48.28 and \$147.75. While differences in purchasing power and cost of living between countries need consideration, Shamiri's delivery system is more scalable than traditional approaches, enhancing its potential to increase access to mental health treatment in resource-restricted LMICs. Also of note, costs associated with transportation time alone for supervisors and lay providers accounted for nearly half (44.7%) of total costs in the base case scenario. (Venturo-Conerly et al., 2021; Kacmarek et al., 2023).

An interviewee mentioned that their team is continuously working on cost reduction by analysing different factors that impact the cost per user. A financial model helps identify cost-heavy areas, with supervision being a major expense in service delivery. In 2023, the cost per user was able to go down to approximately \$7 to \$8, lower than traditional therapy but still likely higher than affordable for the context. To further reduce costs, they are leveraging financial modelling to assess how changes in service delivery impact expenses. They are also exploring the use of technology and conducting small-scale tests, such as adjusting the supervisor-to-fellow ratio, to evaluate cost-saving measures without compromising programme quality.

Context, applicability and scalability:

The intervention is scalable due to its brevity and reliance on lay providers. It has been successfully implemented in different school settings in Kenya, making it accessible to a large number of adolescents in that context. If costs can be reduced, it may be possible to further scale the intervention.

According to studies documenting base costs (Kacmarek et al, 2023), while the Shamiri intervention costs \$15.17 (USD) per student, scaling it to reach thousands of students across multiple regions presents significant challenges. Financial resources would be required to support training, materials, and logistics, particularly in rural and remote areas where poor infrastructure and transportation difficulties hinder implementation. A considerable portion of the intervention's costs is attributed to transportation, as lay providers and supervisors must travel extensively to and from school sites, incurring both time and financial burdens. These high transportation costs could limit the scalability of the programme, especially in geographically dispersed regions. Additionally, although lay providers require only 10 hours of training, maintaining consistent quality and adherence to the intervention protocol remains challenging. Furthermore, ensuring cultural and contextual appropriateness across diverse populations in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) is crucial, as a lack of cultural sensitivity could reduce the intervention's acceptability and overall impact.

According to an interviewee, scaling up the Shamiri intervention presents several key challenges. One major barrier is the difficulty of adapting the intervention to new contexts while maintaining its effectiveness. Although Shamiri was designed with scalability in mind, each setting has unique cultural and contextual factors, and there is limited evidence on the best ways to adapt interventions without compromising outcomes. Additionally, as noted previously, securing funding is a significant obstacle, particularly for newer organisations, as global mental health funding tends to favour well-established programmes and established academic teams while early-stage initiatives struggle to obtain resources for expansion. Another challenge is finding the right implementation partners who share the programme's mission and

have the necessary skills to deliver the intervention effectively. Furthermore, data collection remains a logistical hurdle, as many participants complete assessments on paper rather than digitally, making data entry and analysis time-consuming.

Another interviewee explained that the intervention is designed to be widely scalable and appropriate across various settings. A key advantage is the ability to recruit lay providers at relatively low cost in many contexts and embed the intervention in schools. A significant benefit of the intervention is that it does not rely heavily on professional providers. Instead, only a small number of professionals are needed for supervision and training, which increases its accessibility in regions with limited mental health resources. They consider that the primary challenges would be logistical rather than content related, such as who are the most suitable lay providers for a given setting and is there reliable transportation to reach schools.

They also believe that while the core content of the intervention is unlikely to require significant modification across locations, it is always advisable to consult experts familiar with the specific setting. These experts might include individuals with clinical experience in the region, those who have worked in local schools, or individuals with firsthand experience of mental health challenges in that context. The intervention was chosen for its potential universal applicability, though minor adjustments, such as modifying names, examples, and images, may be necessary to enhance its relevance in different cultural and social settings.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

One interviewee mentioned that the Shamiri Institute emphasises equity by making mental health interventions accessible and culturally relevant for young people in Kenya. Their approach is designed to be low-cost, scalable, and adaptable to local contexts, ensuring that students from diverse backgrounds can benefit. By incorporating character strengths, growth mindset, and gratitude, the intervention supports well-being in an inclusive way.

However, they also mentioned that disability-specific adaptations have not yet been explored. In Kenya, students with disabilities often attend specialised schools, meaning that implementing Shamiri in those settings would require additional modifications. The team has not yet studied how the intervention could be tailored for students with disabilities but recognises the importance of making it more inclusive in the future.

Regarding testing the intervention in other settings, the initial trial was conducted in a n urban area with high population density and poverty and low-level of public infrastructure and resources; interviewees described this to be a typical “slum”. Nevertheless, in 2025 they are preparing to test efficacy in rural areas as they have partners in rural areas and now it is possible to do the comparison between rural and urban areas.

A second interviewee explained that the intervention is school-based, which inherently limits what can be achieved within that setting. While the organisation has considered developing a version that operates outside of schools, such a model would differ significantly from the current approach. As a result, this is not a priority at the moment. However, they are exploring and testing alternative, non-school-based options, though these efforts remain in the early stages and are not yet a core organisational focus.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Implementing and scaling mental health interventions in low-resource settings presents several challenges. Shamiri has faced barriers in adaptation to new contexts, funding constraints, research logistics, and ensuring effectiveness and acceptability. Addressing these obstacles is essential for its long-term success and impact.

- **Scaling Up Across Different Contexts** – While Shamiri was designed for scalability, adapting the intervention to new locations presents challenges. There is limited evidence on how to effectively modify interventions for different populations while maintaining effectiveness. Each context is unique, making it difficult to determine what should be adapted without compromising impact.
- **Funding Challenges** – Securing funding is a major obstacle, particularly for early-stage interventions. While financial support is more available for well-established programmes, newer initiatives like Shamiri struggle to obtain initial funding. Even after proving effectiveness, sustained funding and finding committed implementing partners remain challenges.
- **Logistical Difficulties in Research and Implementation** – Conducting research and scaling up the intervention requires extensive data collection, which is complicated by the reliance on paper-based surveys rather than digital tools. This process is time-consuming and resource-intensive, slowing down research and evaluation efforts.
- **Acceptability** – One reason for training lay providers instead of teachers is that students often do not trust teachers to be involved in mental health provision. Receiving support from others in similar settings and age groups is thus preferential, and can be a lesson for other settings.
- **Understanding Effectiveness and Adaptation** – More research is needed to identify who benefits most from Shamiri and who may require alternative interventions. The lack of clear evidence on moderators of effectiveness makes it difficult to refine the programme and optimise its impact across different groups.
- **Comparative Effectiveness and Larger Studies** – While Shamiri has undergone several randomised controlled trials (RCTs), many early studies had small sample sizes, and there is limited research comparing Shamiri to other interventions. Larger studies and comparative effectiveness research are needed to strengthen the evidence base.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- **To assess the comparative effectiveness and long-term impact** of the Shamiri Intervention, investing in research that directly compares its outcomes to other school-based interventions, including mental health interventions, will provide essential evidence on its relative efficacy. Additionally, long-term studies are necessary to determine whether its benefits are sustained over time, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of its lasting impact.
- **To strengthen the reliability and applicability of findings**, expanding the scale of studies is essential. Larger sample sizes will enhance the robustness of results, while transitioning from paper-based to digital assessments will improve data collection efficiency and facilitate large-scale implementation, particularly in settings where digital access remains limited.
- **To refine the intervention's reach and effectiveness**, identifying which populations benefit most from the Shamiri Intervention will help refine its implementation and ensure targeted impact. Addressing logistical barriers, such as transportation costs and training needs, is also crucial for enabling scalability, particularly in geographically dispersed regions where accessibility remains a challenge.

- **To enhance cultural and contextual adaptability**, further research is needed to explore strategies for modifying the Shamiri Intervention for diverse populations while maintaining its effectiveness. Strengthening cultural sensitivity through evidence-based adaptation will ensure that the intervention remains relevant, acceptable, and impactful across different settings.

Key references:

- Kacmarek, C. N., Johnson, N. E., Osborn, T. L., Wasanga, C., Weisz, J. R., & Yates, B. T. (2023). Costs and cost-effectiveness of Shamiri, a brief, layperson-delivered intervention for Kenyan adolescents: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Health Services Research*, 23(1), 827. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09856-z>
- Osborn, T. L., Wasil, A. R., Venturo-Conerly, K. E., Schleider, J. L., & Weisz, J. R. (2019). Group intervention for adolescent anxiety and depression: Outcomes of a randomized trial with adolescents in Kenya. *Behavior Therapy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beth.2019.09.005>
- Osborn, T. L., Venturo-Conerly, K. E., Arango, S., Roe, E., Rodriguez, M., Alemu, R. G., Gan, J., Wasil, A. R., Otieno, B. H., Rusch, T., & Ndeti, D. M. (2021). Effect of Shamiri Layperson-Provided Intervention vs Study Skills Control Intervention for Depression and Anxiety Symptoms in Adolescents in Kenya: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 78(8), 829-837.
- Osborn, T. L., Venturo-Conerly, K. E., Wasil, A. R., et al. (2020). The Shamiri group intervention for adolescent anxiety and depression: Study protocol for a randomized controlled trial of a lay-provider-delivered, school-based intervention in Kenya. *Trials*, 21, 938. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-020-04732-1>
- Venturo-Conerly et al. (2021). Testing the effects of the Shamiri Intervention and its components on anxiety, depression, wellbeing, and academic functioning in Kenyan adolescents: study protocol for a five-arm randomized controlled trial. *Trials*, 22:829. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-021-05736-1>
- Venturo-Conerly, K., Osborn, T., Weisz, J., Puffer, E., Ndeti, D., Wasanga, C., Rusch, T., & Johnson, N. (2022). Long Term Health Outcomes of Adolescent Character Strength Interventions, 3 – To 4 Year Outcomes of Three Randomized Controlled Trials of the Shamiri Program. *Trials*, 23(443).

SKILLS TRAINING IN AFFECTIVE AND INTERPERSONAL REGULATION FOR ADOLESCENTS (STAIR - A)

Pipeline stage: Scale

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Lead researcher for a STAIR pilot

Target disorders:

Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (STAIR) primarily targets Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), having been specifically developed to address both the emotional dysregulation and interpersonal difficulties commonly associated with trauma responses. The approach is particularly effective for Complex PTSD (C-PTSD), which typically stems from childhood trauma or prolonged/repeated traumatic experiences. The intervention is particularly effective for individuals who have experienced trauma and struggle with managing emotions and maintaining healthy relationships as a result.

Overview of intervention:

Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (STAIR) is a structured, skills-based therapy program designed to help adolescents who have experienced trauma by enhancing emotional regulation and interpersonal functioning. Originally developed for individuals with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and complex trauma. The program typically consists of 8–12 structured sessions delivered in individual or group settings, emphasising two core areas: emotional regulation (teaching skills like distress tolerance, identifying emotions, and self-soothing techniques) and interpersonal effectiveness (helping adolescents improve communication, assertiveness, and boundary-setting). While STAIR is primarily a skills-based intervention, it can be combined with trauma-focused cognitive therapy (TF-CBT) for deeper trauma processing when necessary. This combination allows clients to build a solid foundation of coping skills and emotional stability with STAIR before addressing and reprocessing traumatic experiences directly through TF-CBT, creating a comprehensive approach that can enhance overall treatment outcomes.

Multiple variations of the STAIR intervention have been developed as adaptations to adolescent populations.

- 1) STAIR – Adolescent (STAIR-A) - adapted from the original STAIR manual developed for adult survivors of childhood abuse to be more suitable for the adolescent population (Gudiño et al., 2016).
- 2) STAIR Narrative Therapy (SNT) – STAIR combined with narrative therapy (NT) for patients where longer-term engagement is possible (residential facilities) (Gudiño et al., 2017)
- 3) Brief STAIR - a 3-module version of STAIR developed for adolescents in short-term inpatient care (Gudiño et al., 2014)

The intervention also has other variations such as ESTAIR – Enhanced STAIR version for complex PTSD (Karatzias et al., 2023), a variant for parents, a self-guided edition, and an online model (Cloitre et al., 2024) have also been introduced.

In all variations, STAIR is delivered by trained therapists in mostly clinical and healthcare settings (Gudiño et al., 2017, 2024). One adaptation to a community clinic for adult PTSD clients also showed promising results (MacIntosh et al., 2018). Studies show that STAIR has mostly been implemented and trialed in high-income countries (HIC) such as the United States (Gudiño et al., 2016), the United Kingdom (Karatzias et al., 2023), Germany (Rojas et al., 2022) and Japan (Niwa et al., 2022, p. 11).

Scope:

The review focuses on the use of STAIR with the adolescent populations and aims to provide a comparison between the different variations of the intervention to provide recommendations for wider adoption and scaling into diverse settings, especially Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs).

Intervention development and theory of change:

STAIR was developed in the early 2000s by Cloitre and colleagues at New York University as a response to the complex challenges faced by trauma survivors, particularly those with histories of childhood abuse and PTSD (Cloitre et al., 2002). This intervention integrates principles from cognitive behavioural therapy, dialectical behaviour therapy, and interpersonal as well as attachment theories to specifically target emotional dysregulation and difficulties in interpersonal relationships. Initially designed for adult women, early clinical trials underscored its efficacy in reducing PTSD symptoms, which paved the way for adaptations such as STAIR Narrative Therapy (STAIR-NT) which combines skills training with narrative exposure techniques. Over time, the intervention has been further modified for special populations including adolescents, veterans, and individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds, and it has been successfully delivered both in individual and group formats. More recent developments include digital adaptations, such as mobile applications and telehealth modalities, allowing for broader dissemination and enhanced accessibility (Cloitre et al., 2010; Brown et al., 2015). The adolescent focus intervention **STAIR-A**, was adapted from the original STAIR manual developed for adult survivors of childhood abuse (Gudiño et al., 2016). Adaptations included modifying content from the 10 topics to be developmentally appropriate for adolescents. For example, the psycho-education was modified to be more age-appropriate, the language used to describe concepts and exercises was simplified, and more visual aids were included in handouts. Similarly, examples of stressful situations used to guide discussions or facilitate role plays were modified to be more relevant for adolescents (e.g., dating, gossiping, bullying, problems with parents, concerns about grades, concerns about appropriate sexual behaviours) (Landolt et al., 2024). Furthermore, the sessions were adapted to be delivered in a group format.

STAIR plus Narrative Therapy—Adolescent Version (**SNT-A**) is a two-module cognitive behavioural intervention that begins with a 10-session skills training (STAIR) component followed by 6 sessions of narrative therapy (NT), during which STAIR work continues. The number of sessions to complete the STAIR component can vary depending on the needs of the adolescent; successful skill development may require repeated practice or tailored elaborations. The number of sessions provided during the narrative work will depend on the number of memories and situations that the adolescent and therapist decide to discuss, with the expectation that the narrative work will consist of 6 sessions but may involve additional, typically no more than 4 sessions. SNT-A typically consists of 16 sessions; however, that number may vary depending on the needs of the adolescent and agreed upon goals (Gudiño et al., 2017).

SNT-A was developed to address the multiple problems that individuals with histories of childhood abuse may develop, such as significant problems in emotion regulation and relational capacities (Karatzias et al., 2023). In some settings, due to limited amounts of time available (e.g., inpatient stays), only the skills training component of the treatment (STAIR-A) is implemented (Landolt et al., 2024). However, in other settings, such as outpatient services or school-based programs, the treatment can be extended to include

a review of traumatic events and the creation of a trauma narrative in the context of developing a life story (NT)(Khosravi & Adibi, 2022). As such SNT-A was able to balance between the skill development, that can provide important life skills to help adolescents manage day-to-day experiences, and exposure-based interventions that look back on past experiences and reappraise their meaning, particularly in light of emotional, social, and personal development demonstrated through the skills work (Gudiño et al., 2017).

Brief STAIR -A is a repeatable 3-module version of STAIR developed for adolescents in inpatient care (Gudiño et al., 2014). To increase the fit with the limited engagement time in inpatient care, STAIR was distilled into three 90-minute single-session modules offered once a week. During the pilot implemented in the New York City public hospital, adolescents could start with any module and could attend groups repeatedly throughout their stay (Gudiño et al., 2014). Module 1, adolescents receive psychoeducation about trauma and emotions and they practice monitoring and labelling emotions. Module 2 focuses on coping with difficult feelings. Module 3 focuses on developing skills for clear communication, with adolescents learning to identify barriers to effective communication, acquiring new communication skills, and developing competence and flexibility in interpersonal interactions. skills training interventions targeting stabilisation, functioning, symptom reduction, and safety were prioritised; a trauma narrative was not included.

The Enhanced Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (**ESTAIR**), is a flexible multi-modular approach that focuses on the treatment of C-PTSD and its transdiagnostic symptoms. ESTAIR is consistent with trauma-informed and patient-centred care, which highlights the importance of patient choice in identification and sequencing in targeting C-PTSD symptoms (Karatzias et al., 2023). ESTAIR has adopted all the theoretical and clinical principles of STAIR in line with the ICD-11 formulation of C-PTSD. ESTAIR includes modules to treat all symptom clusters of C-PTSD. Each of the four ESTAIR modules is structurally equivalent (6 sessions each). While the ESTAIR intervention has not been adapted to be used with adolescents yet, given that C-PTSD is diagnosed among young people the intervention has the potential to be adopted to a younger age group.

While most implementation locations for STAIR had been hospital settings, there were some studies conducted in the community (MacIntosh et al., 2018), primary care centres(Ortigo et al., 2020) and online (Cloitre et al., 2024) targeting specific target populations such as community trauma centres, veterans services and children in schools(Ortigo et al., 2020).

Theory of change

STAIR centres on addressing the fundamental disruptions caused by trauma to emotional regulation and interpersonal functioning. This theoretical framework recognises that traumatic experiences, especially those occurring in childhood or within attachment relationships, interfere with the development of crucial skills for identifying and managing emotions, as well as forming healthy relationships. STAIR operates through a sequential process that first builds emotional awareness, tolerance, and regulation capabilities, followed by enhancing interpersonal effectiveness through improved communication and boundary-setting skills. The intervention suggests that by directly targeting these core processes rather than focusing exclusively on traumatic memories, individuals can experience reduced PTSD symptoms, improved daily functioning, and enhanced capacity to engage with trauma-focused work when necessary. This approach acknowledges that sustainable recovery from trauma requires not only processing traumatic experiences but also rebuilding the fundamental emotional and relational capacities that trauma has disrupted.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Several studies, including RCTs, have been carried out to support the general efficacy of STAIR and SNT both among adult and adolescent populations. According to a recent systematic review of seven studies

(Amilhau et al., 2025) STAIR therapy for C-PTSD showed significant symptom reduction, with effect sizes ranging from $d = 1.34$ to 2.29 in clinician assessments and $d = 0.93$ to 2.27 in self-reports. Symptoms of Disturbances in Self-Organisation also decreased in six studies, but comparisons with direct treatments gave varied results, suggesting a complex picture of its effectiveness.

Looking into intervention variation-specific effectiveness information:

Group STAIR

A comparison study within an adult inpatient setting targeting comorbid schizoaffective disorders (Trappler & Newville, 2007) found that clients who received the STAIR group treatment showed significant improvement on measures of PTSD and psychotic symptoms, as well as improvements in affect and emotional expression and management, in contrast to a group treatment as usual condition.

Two RCTs measured the effectiveness of Group STAIR in 1) community sample and 2) veteran sample, both with good outcomes. The community study evaluated the effectiveness of group STAIR with limited training among providers in an outpatient program for survivors of childhood trauma (Gudiño et al., 2016). Qualitative outcomes provided reports of high ease of delivery among members of the mental health team and high satisfaction among the clients. Significant reductions in PTSD, emotion dysregulation, dissociation, and interpersonal problems were observed.

The second study evaluated Group STAIR in a VA PTSD clinic in which male and female veterans ($n=39$) (including those with sexual trauma) participated together (Jackson et al., 2019). Both statistically and clinically significant reductions were obtained in PTSD (Post-traumatic Stress Checklist (PCL) (Cohen's $d = 0.91$)) and general distress symptoms (Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI) (Cohen's $d = 0.90$)), suggesting not only the benefits of STAIR but also the option of providing mixed-gender groups.

Stair and Narrative Therapy (SNT)

An initial RCT of SNT for women adult survivors of childhood abuse with PTSD relative to a waitlist control condition, showed superior outcomes for PTSD and other trauma-related outcomes relative to a waitlist (Cloitre et al., 2002). Results indicated that SNT participants demonstrated significant improvements in PTSD symptoms, affect regulation, interpersonal problems, perceived social support, and overall functioning in family, work, and social domains; gains were maintained at 3- and 9-month follow-up periods (Cloitre et al., 2002; Ortigo et al., 2020).

An RCT of SNT with adult survivors of childhood abuse indicated that the combination of STAIR and Narrative Therapy compared with two control conditions in which each active component was eliminated and replaced with an active nonspecific treatment (Cloitre et al., 2010). Results indicated that compared to STAIR, SNT were more likely to achieve sustained and full remission of PTSD and demonstrated greater improvements in emotion regulation and interpersonal functioning, particularly at the 3- and 6-month follow-up assessments (Ortigo et al., 2020).

The latest RCT evaluated the use of a five-session STAIR for Primary Care (STAIR-PC) delivered to veterans with PTSD symptoms and a range of traumas seeking care in a primary care setting. Given its brevity, the treatment goals focused on quickly identifying the most appropriate tools or skills for specific problems for which the veteran sought treatment. Compared with treatment as usual in primary care, STAIR-PC was found to reduce PTSD symptoms, emotion regulation problems, and social engagement difficulties (Ortigo et al., 2020)

An RCT comparing SNT to prolonged exposure (PE) and intensive PE (iPE) among women with PTSD related to childhood abuse found that the three treatment conditions provided substantial and equivalent reductions in PTSD (Oprel et al., 2021). However, a moderator analysis indicated that those with childhood

sexual abuse (CSA) did less well than those without CSA in the two PE treatment conditions but did equally well in the STAIR+PE condition indicating better outcomes associated with STAIR+PE for this subgroup of individuals.

Lastly, a recent RCT of STAIR alone compared to Person Centered Therapy (PCT) among women veterans with military sexual trauma (MST) and multiple other types of traumas found that STAIR was superior to PCT in reducing PTSD, depression, and trauma-related cognitions and in improving emotion regulation and social support perceptions (Cloitre et al. 2024).

Furthermore, SNT implementation with survivors of the 9/11 World Trade Center terrorist attack indicated significant improvements in PTSD, depression, and interpersonal problems, with equivalent effect sizes to those demonstrated in the first RCT presented earlier (Cloitre et al., 2002). This study helped to demonstrate the utility of SNT for adult-onset trauma and not just childhood trauma.

STAIR-A

Concerning adolescent-focused STAIR, the treatment has been empirically evaluated in a group format both with and without the narrative component in two settings. (Gudiño et al., 2017).

A quasi-experimental study in a school setting assessed the effectiveness of SNT-A as an afterschool programme relative to a matched assessment-only comparison group among girls (N = 46; ages 11–16) and examined multiple stressful or traumatic events faced by students from racial/ethnic minority backgrounds (Gudiño et al., 2016). Girls in the intervention condition (n = 23) received 16 sessions of SNT-A group format, whereas girls in the matched comparison condition (n = 23) only completed assessments at scheduled intervals. Relative to girls in the assessment-only condition, girls participating in SNT-A evidenced statistically and clinically significant improvements posttreatment on indicators of resiliency, including improved social engagement (d = 0.65) and locus of control (d = 0.46) and marginally significant improvement in interpersonal relations (d = -0.46). Girls receiving the intervention also evidenced significant reductions in depressive symptoms (d = 0.58) post-treatment and marginally significant reductions in anxiety symptoms (d = 0.42) relative to the assessment-only group. Treatment gains were largely maintained after three months, with scores for depression, anxiety, and social stress remaining significantly improved relative to baseline (Gudiño et al., 2017).

Post-hoc analyses revealed a trend whereby girls who had clinically elevated levels of PTSD at baseline and showed higher levels of engagement with the trauma narrative (i.e., completed the homework and were willing to talk about their reactions during sessions) experienced reductions in PTSD symptoms relative to girls who were less engaged (Ortigo et al., 2020). Taken as a whole, results from this study suggest that SNT-A delivered to high-risk girls can successfully enhance resilience and reduce symptoms of psychopathology.

Brief STAIR

The efficacy of Brief STAIR which uses a skills-only and shortened version of STAIR was examined in an open trial of adolescent psychiatric inpatients exposed to multiple traumatic events (Gudiño et al., 2024). An uncontrolled design was used to conduct a preliminary examination of the group intervention's effectiveness. Adolescent psychiatric inpatients (N = 38; ages 12 years–17 years) admitted to a public hospital participated in Brief STAIR-A and attended a median of 6 sessions (range 3–36). They completed measures of PTSD and depressive symptom severity, coping skill use, and coping efficacy upon admission and again prior to discharge. Participants reported significant reductions in symptom severity (d = 0.65–0.67), no change in the absolute level of coping skills used (d = 0.16), but greater coping efficacy when discharged from care (d = 0.75). Results from this pilot study suggest that this brief group treatment shows

promise for treating adolescents' trauma-related difficulties in inpatient psychiatry settings (Gudiño et al., 2014).

A growing body of research—including randomised controlled trials and systematic reviews—supports the efficacy of STAIR and its variants in treating symptoms of PTSD and Complex PTSD. The studies reported significant reductions in both clinician-assessed and self-reported symptoms, with notable effect sizes. Additionally, while the intervention shows robust improvements in emotional and interpersonal regulation, outcomes for disturbances in self-organisation are more variable when compared with treatments that directly target trauma processing. In one study referenced, even clients with comorbid psychotic symptoms (in a group STAIR format) showed significant improvements. Overall, the evidence suggests that STAIR is an effective, versatile intervention that, depending on the clinical context and population, can produce meaningful changes in symptomatology and functioning.

Relevance to PLE:

STAIR is a phase-based intervention that requires collaboration with the clients to move from one phase to the other. The design of the intervention requires that the selection of the modules and direction of the recovery journey need to be taken by the clients themselves (Ortigo et al., 2020). Furthermore, STAIR is a skill-building intervention therefore, it provides the skills for clients to not only reconcile with past traumatic experiences but also empower them with skills for future challenges as well. The intervention has also adapted its methodology to suit different engagement levels. The STAIR sessions are designed as practical discussions and roleplay to ensure that participants are able to participate and explore (Cloitre et al., 2002) using their own experiences. The dose of the intervention is collectively determined by the client and the therapist, giving them a sense of control over their own intervention journey.

The level of PLE engagement in the design and implementation of the intervention is not clear in the published literature however, the interview acknowledged that such involvement were not carried out. Given that STAIR is delivered by therapists or trained professionals capable of supporting adults and young people who have experienced C-PTSD there have not been attempts thus far for the intervention to be peer-delivered.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

The resource requirements change based on the variation of STAIR that is chosen for implementation. SNT is a longer, more resource-intensive process in comparison to the Brief STAIR version. The over-the-phone support provision of STAIR is one of the most cost-effective. However, the most significant resource requirement is the training of the therapists and other professionals for the implementation of the intervention. Given the sensitivity and vulnerability of the target populations, adequate training and supervision of the implementers are important aspects. Furthermore, given that the intervention is modularised, if implemented in a new location the modules will have to be translated and adapted to the context. This can be a resource-intensive process.

STAIR has not conducted cost-effectiveness studies, therefore it is difficult to provide empirical evidence. However, the current evidence highlights an increase in functionality of the participants post-intervention, resulting in potentially more productive members of their community. The skill development components also have the potential to empower participants to navigate day-to-day challenges reducing the burden on the health system and the professionals.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Thus far STAIR interventions have been implemented in dominantly HICs (USA, UK, Japan) with strong and well-resourced health systems. For example, STAIR-A was delivered as part of standard care on an

inpatient unit in New York, where dropping out entirely from treatment was improbable. Therefore, the low attrition rate of such studies is a testament to the intervention's acceptability and feasibility in the treatment for inpatient settings rather than to acceptability by individual patients and families. (Gudiño et al., 2014)

Similarly in such contexts, the mental health literacy of the population can also be at a relatively advanced stage making the discussion-based modules more feasible. On the other hand adverse events around the world have increased with conflicts and natural disasters increasing the risk of exposure to trauma at a population level, especially in LMICs.

The intervention and the skills that it focuses on are applicable in most contexts where populations experience trauma. However, the relevant human resources may not be present in low-resource settings. Especially those with previous training in supporting persons experiencing PTSD might be limited. Furthermore, the current intervention design finds potential participants through service access points (healthcare settings, hospitals, clinics, and schools). In some contexts where mental health, abuse and sexual violence are considered taboo and stigmatising, the intervention might not be able to reach the participants through services.

To understand the scalability of the STAIR intervention, its implementation in LMIC settings need to be evaluated further.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

While there is increasing emphasis on community-based mental health care (World Health Organization, 2013), inpatient treatment is a necessary part of the continuum of services, especially for those with severe difficulties (Cloitre et al., 2002). Persons experiencing C-PTSD due to exposure to trauma may require such specialised support. As such these services can present an opportunity to identify the effect of trauma on these difficulties and to begin to address such problems (Gudiño et al., 2014). Without such services people experiencing trauma may end up in long-term care facilities. Given that potential compounding effects of complex trauma could make people vulnerable and susceptible to unhealthy coping and mental health conditions. This is evident by the fact that the prevalence of C-PTSD ranges from 3.9 % to 8.8 % in the general population, however its prevalence among psychiatric patients is 36 % and a higher incidence in women, who tend to experience more severe psychological distress (Niwa et al., 2022). Among adolescents, studies found C-PTSD rates ranging from 2.4 % to 12.3 % (Amilhau et al., 2025).

As such a skill-building intervention such as STAIR has the potential to empower participants to face not only the challenges of past trauma but also gain skills to face future ones (Jackson et al., 2019). By empowering persons with C-PTSD and equipping them with emotional, and relational skills as well as a sense of identity, the intervention could reduce the vulnerability of the participants. Therefore, STAIR can play an important role in bridging the treatment gap for some of the most vulnerable populations.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

STAIR has been demonstrated as an effective intervention with moderate to large effect sizes for Group STAIR and SNT among both adults and adolescents for PTSD and also for depression, anxiety and daily functioning. Given that it has been successfully tested in multiple settings the intervention is currently within the "scale" level of the pipeline.

Among the factors that facilitated the implementation of the intervention is the flexibility of the module structure where therapists along with the participants are able to make decisions and tailor the intervention to meet the participant's individual needs. In addition, STAIR intervention is able to provide a sense of validation of the emotions and experiences faced by the participants. Especially when they belong to vulnerable or marginalised communities and their trauma experience is linked to that as well. Given that

STAIR is also a skills training intervention the engagement between the therapist and the participant is crucial. The way that the intervention is organised with discussions, roleplays and real-world skill application, therapists can foster trust and guide adolescents toward healthier coping mechanisms, enhancing engagement and skill acquisition and real-life applicability.

In terms of the barriers to implementation, the adaptable structure of the intervention became a challenge for some therapists to adapt the intervention to diverse needs, symptoms and skill levels. In addition, participants from racial, ethnic, and sexual or gender minority (SGM) groups may present with stressors related to discrimination, stigma, and identity-based trauma. While STAIR is well-suited for addressing daily minority stressors, it cannot directly change systemic discrimination or structural racism. Therapists need to be sensitive to these issues while ensuring a safe therapeutic environment. Participants may also rely on maladaptive coping mechanisms which can be challenging to change into adaptive ones. STAIR also encourages participants to aim using novel sets of skills which may be received with a sense of scepticism and need to be managed through experiential learning.

Implementing STAIR presents both challenges and opportunities. While therapists may encounter difficulties in flexibility, skill adoption, and addressing trauma, they can enhance treatment success through validation, structured adaptability, experiential learning, and a strong understanding of intervention principles.

Recommendations for investment:

STAIR is being implemented with positive results in HIC settings and needs to bridge certain evidence gaps to scale up to other settings, especially LMICs. In this regard, given below are some recommendations for future investment.

Research Recommendations

- **Further studies to compare STAIR interventions with other similar therapeutic models.** While the efficacy of STAIR is well documented it would be important to understand its impact in comparison to other interventions supporting similar disorders. For example comparison between STAIR and Interpersonal Psychotherapy (IPT) or mindfulness-based therapies will help to determine its relative effectiveness. Especially since the intervention has rarely been used in LMIC setting such evidence will be able to meaningfully guide its potential scaling options. Ideally, such research should assess multiple outcomes, including symptom reduction, dropout rates, and patient satisfaction to gain the context-specific understanding.
- **Use innovative evaluation methodologies to understand the adaptive qualities.** Given that the intervention is a phase-based intervention that is to be adapted to the participant needs, the implementation of STAIR changes from patient to patient especially the sequence of the modules and their dosage. As such evaluating the intervention using the same methodologies that are designed for interventions with strict implementation protocols may not capture the benefits of an adaptive approach. As such methodologies such as “Sequential, Multiple Assignment Randomized Trials” (SMART) designs could be implemented to evaluate the adaptive treatment sequences, modifying interventions based on participant responses (Karatzias et al., 2023).
- Undertake further implementation evaluation in diverse community settings to assess real-world effectiveness and accessibility. Thus far STAIR has mostly been implemented in high-income clinical settings. Therefore, there may be challenges of adaptability, applicability and cultural sensitivity when scaling the intervention. Variation in the presentation of PTSD symptoms across different cultures is a major consideration in this regard where modifications might be necessary to ensure cross-cultural

relevance and accessibility. Therefore, evaluation of the implementation in community settings in LMICs would provide a better understanding of the intervention's applicability in diverse settings.

- **Tailor to population needs.** Given the increasing need for support to manage trauma in diverse settings in the face of conflicts, marginalisation and exploitation of vulnerable groups, interventions such as STAIR would need to scale into nonclinical settings to meet the needs of such populations. Therefore, further engagement and adaptation to diverse populations, including veterans, women, LGBTQ individuals, parents, and adolescents, will support to adapt STAIR while ensuring its relevance across various demographic settings.

Ecosystems Recommendations

- **Explore digital and telehealth adaptations.** Many vulnerable and underserved populations find it difficult to access interventions that meet complex needs such as for PTSD given the need for high-capacity technical human resources. As such investing in digital and telehealth adaptations of STAIR, such as mobile applications, online self-directed modules, and therapist-assisted virtual formats, can improve accessibility for underserved populations, including those in rural areas.

Key references:

- Alisic, E., Zalta, A. K., Wesel, F. van, Larsen, S. E., Hafstad, G. S., Hassanpour, K., & Smid, G. E. (2014). Rates of post-traumatic stress disorder in trauma-exposed children and adolescents: Meta-analysis. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 204(5), 335–340. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.113.131227>
- Amilhau, A., Soubelet, A., Crozier, L., & Colamarino, L. (2025). Skills training in affective and interpersonal regulation (STAIR) for treating complex trauma: A systematic review. *European Journal of Trauma & Dissociation*, Volume 9,(Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejtd.2024.100493>
- Cloitre, M., Koenen, K. C., Cohen, L. R., & Han, H. (2002). Skills training in affective and interpersonal regulation followed by exposure: A phase-based treatment for PTSD related to childhood abuse. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 70(5), 1067–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006X.70.5.1067>
- Cloitre, M., Morabito, D., Macia, K., Speicher, S., Froelich, J., Webster, K., Prins, A., Villasenor, D., Bauer, A., Jackson, C., Fabricant, L., Wiltsey-Stirman, S., & Morland, L. (2024). A home-based telehealth randomized controlled trial of skills training in affective and interpersonal regulation versus present-centered therapy for women veterans who have experienced military sexual trauma. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 92(5), 261–274. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ccp0000872>
- Cloitre, M., Stovall-McClough, K. C., Nooner, K., Zorbas, P., Cherry, S., Jackson, C. L., Gan, W., & Petkova, E. (2010). Treatment for PTSD Related to Childhood Abuse: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 167(8), 915–924. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2010.09081247>
- Gudiño, O. G., Leonard, S., & Cloitre, M. (2016). STAIR-A for Girls: A Pilot Study of a Skills-Based Group for Traumatized Youth in an Urban School Setting. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Trauma*, 9(1), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-015-0061-0>
- Gudiño, O. G., Leonard, S., Stiles, A. A., Havens, J. F., & Cloitre, M. (2017). STAIR narrative therapy for adolescents. In *Evidence-based treatments for trauma related disorders in children and adolescents* (pp. 251–271). Springer International Publishing/Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46138-0_12
- Gudiño, O. G., Leonard, S., Stiles, A. A., Havens, J. F., & Cloitre, M. (2024). STAIR Narrative Therapy for Adolescents. In M. A. Landolt, M. Cloitre, & U. Schnyder (Eds.), *Evidence-Based Treatments for Trauma-Related Disorders in Children and Adolescents* (pp. 319–341). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77215-3_12
- Gudiño, O. G., Weis, J. R., Havens, J. F., Biggs, E. A., Diamond, U. N., Marr, M., Jackson, C., & Cloitre, M. (2014). Group Trauma-Informed Treatment for Adolescent Psychiatric Inpatients: A Preliminary Uncontrolled Trial. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*, 27(4), 496–500. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jts.21928>
- Jackson, C., Weiss, B. J., & Cloitre, M. (2019). STAIR Group Treatment for Veterans with PTSD: Efficacy and Impact of Gender on Outcome. *Military Medicine*, 184(1–2), e143–e147. <https://doi.org/10.1093/milmed/usy164>
- Karatzias, T., Mc Glanaghy, E., & Cloitre, M. (2023). Enhanced Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (ESTAIR): A New Modular Treatment for ICD-11 Complex Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (CPTSD). *Brain Sciences*, 13(9), Article 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci13091300>
- Khosravi, M., & Adibi, A. (2022). STAIR Plus Narrative Therapy-Adolescent Version (SNT-A) in An 11-Year-Old Girl With PTSD and Suicidal Behaviors Following Rape/Sexual Assault: A Case Report. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Trauma*, 15(3), 943–948. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-021-00430-5>

- Knipschild, R., Klip, H., van Leeuwen, D., van Onna, M. J. R., Lindauer, R. J. L., Staal, W. G., Bicanic, I. A. E., & de Jongh, A. (2023). Treatment of multiple traumatized adolescents by enhancing regulation skills and reducing trauma related symptoms: Rationale, study design, and methods of randomized controlled trial (the Mars-study). *BMC Psychiatry*, 23(1), 644. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-05073-4>
- Landolt, M. A., Cloitre, M., & Schnyder, U. (Eds.). (2024). *Evidence-Based Treatments for Trauma-Related Disorders in Children and Adolescents*. Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77215-3>
- MacIntosh, H. B., Cloitre, M., Kortis, K., Peck, A., & Weiss, B. J. (2018). Implementation and Evaluation of the Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (STAIR) in a Community Setting in the Context of Childhood Sexual Abuse. *Research on Social Work Practice*, 28(5), 595–602. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049731516656803>
- Marylène, C. (n.d.). *Clinician's Corner Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (STAIR)*. International Society for Traumatic Stress Studies. Retrieved March 18, 2025, from <https://istss.org/clinicians-corner-skills-training-in-affective-and-interpersonal-regulation-stair-marylène-cloitre-phd/>
- Niwa, M., Kato, T., Narita-Ohtaki, R., Otomo, R., Suga, Y., Sugawara, M., Narita, Z., Hori, H., Kamo, T., & Kim, Y. (2022). Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation Narrative Therapy for women with ICD-11 complex PTSD related to childhood abuse in Japan: A pilot study. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 13(1), 2080933. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20008198.2022.2080933>
- Oprel, D. A. C., Hoeboer, C. M., Schoorl, M., de Kleine, R. A., Cloitre, M., Wigard, I. G., van Minnen, A., & van der Does, W. (2021). Effect of Prolonged Exposure, intensified Prolonged Exposure and STAIR+Prolonged Exposure in patients with PTSD related to childhood abuse: A randomized controlled trial. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 12(1), 1851511. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20008198.2020.1851511>
- Ortigo, K. M., Bauer, A., & Cloitre, M. (2020). Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (STAIR) Narrative Therapy: Making meaning while learning skills. In M. T. Tull & N. A. Kimbrel (Eds.), *Emotion in Posttraumatic Stress Disorder* (pp. 513–543). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-816022-0.00018-1>
- Rojas, R., Hitzler, M., Palmer, S., Sauer, K. S., Wendler-Bödicker, C., Boos, A., Hoyer, J., & Niemeyer, H. (2022). Complex Trauma Symptoms after Childhood Maltreatment: Strengths and Challenges of the Therapy Program STAIR-NT. *Verhaltenstherapie*, 32(Suppl. 1), 220–229. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000526594>
- Trappler, B., & Newville, H. (2007). Trauma Healing Via Cognitive Behavior Therapy in Chronically Hospitalized Patients. *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 78(4), 317–325. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11126-007-9049-8>
- World Health Organization. (2013). Mental health action plan 2013-2020. In *Plan d'action global pour la santé mentale 2013-2020*. World Health Organization. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/89966>

PEER SUPPORT (AS PER USING PEER SUPPORT IN DEVELOPING EMPOWERING MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES PROJECT - UPSIDES)

Pipeline stage: Scale

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Member of the UPSIDES Consortium, collaborator and consultant for co-design of the intervention
- Member of the implementation team in Uganda

Target disorders:

Peer support can be considered a transdiagnostic task-sharing approach that targets better treatment adherence and recovery of persons with a range of severe mental health conditions, such as psychosis, major depression and bipolar disorders (C. I. Mahlke et al., 2017). In many contexts, the principles of peer support have also been adapted to increase treatment adherence and recovery through a person-centred approach (Charles et al., 2020; Mpango et al., 2020; UPSIDES, n.d.).

The UPSIDES peers support intervention (PSI) involved individuals with severe mental illnesses—such as schizophrenia, severe depression, and bipolar disorder—characterised by long-term conditions that significantly impair daily functioning. It used peer support, drawing on shared lived experiences, to aid recovery, social inclusion, empowerment, and clinical outcomes (Puschner et al., 2019).

Overview of intervention:

Peer support interventions involve Peer Support Workers (PSWs)—individuals with lived experience of mental health conditions who are trained to use skills and experiences gained in their recovery journey to support others. PSW are always PLE of specific mental health conditions; PSWs can therefore draw on their lived experience as well as other skills to provide emotional and practical support, condition management, or engage in advocacy, coaching, and outreach. By sharing personal experiences and fostering hope, empowerment, and self-efficacy, PSWs promote both their own recovery and that of others (Puschner et al., 2019). Peer support may be delivered independently or as part of formal mental health services (Nixdorf et al., 2024).

PSI have gained popularity in high-income countries (HICs), particularly among service users and researchers advocating for its integration into mental health systems. Countries such as the USA, UK, Australia, New Zealand, and Canada have noted the benefits of peer support in policy (Puschner et al., 2019). New roles—such as peer companions, peer advocates, and peer counsellors—have emerged to formally recognise PSWs within mental health services. In some settings, PSWs are introduced as “Life teachers” to safeguard them from the stigma of mental health. There is high heterogeneity in how PSI are implemented in practice, and especially for LMICs. UPSIDES was developed to bridge this gap.

The UPSIDES programme is a standardised, multi-national initiative co-developed by scientists, mental health professionals, PSWs and service users across six countries. It aims to scale up PSI for people with severe mental illness by adapting them to high-, middle-, and low-resource settings and local cultural contexts (Hiltensperger, Ryan, et al., 2024). The training includes 12 core modules on key topics like Recovery, Communication, and Community, delivered through participatory methods that promote

discussion and the sharing of lived experiences. Optional modules—such as Stigma, Rights and Advocacy, Trauma, and Financial Empowerment—allow for local adaptation based on community needs.

Training typically takes place over five non-consecutive days, with each day involving eight hours of learning. This structure is intentionally designed to provide rest days between sessions, allowing participants time to absorb the material (C. Mahlke et al., 2020). Module delivery is flexible: while each module can be completed in one day, they can also be split over multiple days to accommodate participant needs. To support global learning and collaboration, an online platform connects trainers, PSWs, and staff across countries for training, supervision, and knowledge exchange (Moran et al., 2020).

Following the training, PSWs work with individuals using a printed participant workbook, which is required for all users. This workbook supports the delivery of a standardised intervention, with each activity tied to a specific training module. For instance, in the Recovery module, PSWs lead a “Tree of Life” activity where individuals reflect on their recovery journey—using metaphors such as roots for origins, trunk for strengths, branches for dreams, and leaves for important relationships. The training manual provides step-by-step guidance to help PSWs facilitate these sessions effectively and meaningfully.

Scope:

This deep dive on PSIs will focus on the UPSIDES intervention, developed through a 5-year (2018 - 2022) project aimed at widening access to PSIs for people with *severe mental illness*.

Intervention development and theory of change:

PSIs have emerged as a vital component of mental health care, rooted in the understanding that individuals with lived experience of mental health conditions are uniquely positioned to support others facing similar challenges. The premise of PSIs is that individuals in recovery can offer valuable insights, practical assistance, and emotional support, fostering trust and open communication in ways that traditional mental health professionals may not be able to achieve (UPSIDES, n.d.).

The origins of PSIs lie in informal, user-led care initiatives that emphasised mutual aid and shared experiences. Over time, with a growing focus on recovery-oriented and person-centred approaches within statutory mental health services, these interventions have become more formalised, structured and sometimes led by staff, at the risk of losing the peer-led model (C. I. Mahlke et al., 2017).

Key facilitators and barriers related to these interventions were identified through a systematic review of 53 PSIs among adults with mental health problems (online databases (n = 11), journal table of contents (n= 2), conference proceedings (n= 18), peer support websites (n = 2), expert consultation (n= 38) and forward and backward citation tracking) (Ibrahim et al., 2020). The primary challenge identified was that PSIs often placed PSWs in paraclinical or substitute roles. This meant that in spaces with traditional workplace hierarchies, PSWs were seen as outsiders and carried a stigma about their legitimacy for engagement with peers. This was at times avoided by orienting PSWs into medical ways of working at the risk of leading to an identity conflict between being a person with lived experience (PLE) on one hand and being a hired professional on the other.

A 2020 systematic review of 39 PSIs on the modifications made to their typology to facilitate implementation identified six types of alterations: 1) clarity on the role expectations, 2) training provided to PSWs before taking on the role, 3) the mode of engaging with service users 4) flexibility beyond traditional PSW role 5) workplace support for PSWs 6) PSW recruitment modalities (Charles et al., 2020). The two strongest modification themes used for LMIC settings were: role expectations and initial training, with the subthemes of: materials used with service users; structure; and topics covered. Building on this evidence, the study recommended that to facilitate scalable interventions, PSIs should use manualised approaches.

This would further enable evaluation of whether the intervention was replicable or the level of adaptation required.

Building on this evidence, UPSIDES was developed as a manualised, comprehensive peer support intervention with a focus on adjunctive peer support, delivering structured behavioural interventions or flexible, socially oriented recovery support. This is a shift because it creates PSIs that are thus autonomous from mental health services and specifically focused on complementary supports.

The UPSIDES process was initiated in 2018 as a 5-year study, with input from academics, professionals, stakeholders, and peers across 6 study locations. UPSIDES study sites included Ulm & Hamburg (Germany), Butabika & Dar es Salaam (Uganda), Beer Sheva (Israel), and Pune (India), which included low, middle and high-income countries. The intervention was developed through extensive consultations using the Theory of Change (TOC) approach. Site-specific TOCs were integrated into a Cross-site TOC map, refined iteratively with academic insights and implementer feedback (Hiltensperger, Ryan, et al., 2024). TOCs helped (a) identify peer support features, (b) establish shared implementation approaches, and (c) account for contextual adaptations. Each site had a Local Advisory Board (LAB) overseeing three phases: (1) preparation and pilot, (2) implementation, and (3) sustainability (Hiltensperger, Ryan, et al., 2024).

Comprehensive training and tools for PSWs were key to intervention success, according to an interviewed member of the UPSIDES Consortium. The training package was informed by a systematic review, local partner experiences, LAB input, and focus groups (C. Mahlke et al., 2020). Existing PSIs contributing to UPSIDES development included ImROC training (UK), Ex-IN curriculum (Germany), Brain Gain projects (Uganda), QualityRights (WHO, India), Healthy Options project (Tanzania), Peer2Peer (Europe), and Yozma Derech-Halev training (Israel) (Moran et al., 2020).

After a six-week pilot phase, trainers, PSWs, and service users finalised the manual (available here: [UPSIDES Manual](#)). Overall, UPSIDES development relied on coproduction at every step of the way, ensuring that the intervention is applicable and relevant to PSW and peers themselves. However, it must also be recognised that the development process has been resource-intensive and costly, making replication in other settings a challenge.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

There is growing evidence for PSIs, particularly in high-income countries such as the USA, UK, Canada, Australia, and Ireland, with one study from Libya representing upper-middle-income settings (Charles et al., 2020). Across 39 studies—including RCTs, qualitative, and observational designs—PSIs were found to help address workforce shortages through task-sharing in overstretched mental health systems. While results varied due to intervention heterogeneity, small sample sizes, and methodological limitations, one-to-one peer support by trained PSWs showed improvements in self-efficacy over 12 months (C. I. Mahlke et al., 2017).

Meta-analyses have reported mixed but promising outcomes. For depression, peer support was more effective than usual care (SMD = -0.59), though not significantly different from group CBT (Pfeiffer et al., 2011). Another review found modest benefits for recovery (SMD = 0.22) and empowerment (SMD = 0.23), with no significant effects on hospitalisation, symptoms, or functioning (White et al., 2020).

Despite inconsistencies, PSIs have been linked to improved empowerment (van Gestel-Timmermans et al., 2012), hope (Schrank et al., 2012), social relationships, recovery, and reduced readmissions in some models (Johnson et al., 2018; Rivera et al., 2007; C. I. Mahlke et al., 2017). When supported by proper

training and access to professional care, peer support is considered a safe and valuable component of mental health services

However, evidence on the UPSIDES PSI is emerging. There has been one multi-centre pragmatic parallel group RCT conducted on UPSIDES across the six study sites (UPSIDES-RCT). The primary outcome of UPSIDES is social inclusion, and secondary outcomes are empowerment, hope, recovery, and health and social functioning. Outcomes were measured at four time points over one year (baseline, 4-month, 8-month, and 12-month follow-ups), with an embedded process evaluation and cost-effectiveness analysis (Moran et al., 2020). The primary outcome, social inclusion among service users with severe mental illness (N = 558; approximately N = 93 per site), was assessed at the 8-month follow-up, while secondary outcomes included empowerment, hope, recovery, and health and social functioning (Moran et al., 2020). However, the outcome data from the RCT have yet to be published (last checked 19 May 2025, www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN26008944).

To evaluate the implementation process, UPSIDES employed implementation research tools, including the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR), to identify facilitators and barriers to intervention delivery. Five key enablers were identified: (i) improving the applicability of training through clearer guidance and structured programme management, (ii) allocating sufficient time for training, (iii) addressing negative attitudes toward peer support workers through additional training for organisations and staff, (iv) incorporating core competencies such as communication skills into the training manual, and (v) considering cultural differences related to mental health services, stigma, and societal discrimination (Nixdorf et al., 2024).

A Fidelity Scale was also developed to document the implementation of UPSIDES across multiple settings. This scale was created through an iterative process involving international expert consultations, site-level feedback, and translation. The final version included a 28-item service user-rated scale and a 21-item peer support worker-rated scale, assessing domains such as receipt, engagement, enactment, competence, communication, and peer support-specific components (Hiltensperger, Kotera, et al., 2024). Internal consistency for both versions was adequate (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.675$ to 0.969), and confirmatory factor analysis indicated an acceptable fit for the service user version ($\chi^2/df = 2.746$; RMSEA = 0.084) and a moderate fit for the peer support worker version ($\chi^2/df = 3.087$; RMSEA = 0.093) (Hiltensperger, Kotera, et al., 2024).

Additionally, UPSIDES developed a rigorous methodology for translating, cross-culturally adapting, and validating study materials, including standardised measures. The UPSIDES Proportionate Translation Methodology consists of ten steps: (Charles et al., 2022).

1. Preparation: All required materials are gathered, including prior translations, and an expert local group—including bilingual speakers—is established.
2. Forward translation: Materials, including instructions and rating scales, are translated into the target language, with the primary outcome measure translated independently by two individuals.
3. Reconciliation: The expert panel reviews and finalises the translation.
4. Back translation: The target version is translated back into the source language.
5. Back translation review: Focuses on conceptual and cultural equivalence rather than direct linguistic accuracy.
6. Harmonisation: A cross-site meeting is held to discuss discrepancies and ensure consistency across translations.
7. Pretesting: Up to five individuals from the target population test the materials and provide feedback.

8. Finalisation: Revisions are made based on pretest findings in collaboration with local teams.
9. Psychometric evaluation: Up to 20 bilingual participants complete both the translated and reordered source versions, enabling assessment of validity and reliability.
10. Dissemination: Final materials are prepared in a non-editable format and shared across study sites.

The translated primary outcome measure for the UPSIDES trial, the Social Inclusion Scale, demonstrated adequate content validity (49.3 vs. 48.5, $p = 0.08$), strong convergent validity, and satisfactory internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.73$), with minimal floor and ceiling effects (Charles et al., 2022).

Research Gaps

PSIs are highly heterogeneous, varying in content, target populations, mode of delivery (individual or group; face-to-face or online), support from mental health services, and provider training. This variability limits the generalisability of findings and highlights the need for more focused reviews of similar intervention types. Although reporting quality has improved, especially regarding trial design and intervention description, further progress is needed—particularly in reporting outcome measures—to strengthen the evidence base for service providers and policymakers (Charles et al., 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Lloyd-Evans et al., 2014; Pitt et al., 2013; White et al., 2020). Data comparing PSIs with clinical care remain limited, as does evidence on cost-effectiveness. Most existing reviews are based on studies from high-income countries (HICs), leaving the effectiveness of PSIs in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) uncertain.

In the case of UPSIDES, the most significant need is to assess effectiveness of the intervention, particularly its sustainability beyond the initial project period in pilot locations. Additionally, given the resource-intensive process of the initial development and pilot, future studies should explore the sustainability of the intervention, particularly in LMICs, and its cost-effectiveness. This includes the effectiveness of scaling UPSIDES into new locations within the pilot countries, where at least some of the initial adaptation costs may be spared. Given that co-production is a core element of UPSIDES, the impact of the intervention on PSWs themselves warrants further investigation. While the UPSIDES-RCT protocol has outlined a comprehensive assessment of these, most outcome data are not published yet.

Lastly, UPSIDES currently targets individuals with severe mental health conditions. However, in LMICs—where care is often community-based—evaluating its relevance for people with mild to moderate symptoms is important. Restricting the intervention to severe cases risks reinforcing stigma and limiting its broader applicability.

Relevance to PLE:

In consultations with PLE, there was a general consensus that PSIs improved social connectedness and contributed towards improved social functioning and a sense of wellbeing. PLE noted that peers were able to empathise and understand not just the mental health challenges that were experienced, but also the wider social issues associated with suffering from severe mental illness. Most studies on PSI had focused on the experience of PSW as the PLE engagement and had not focused on the service user-related experience. Looking at the systematic reviews on PSIs, it is clear that most older interventions had PLE engagement (in the form of PSWs) in paraclinical roles, and/ or in substitute roles. In contrast, newer studies focus on PLE providing adjunctive interventions, either structured, behavioural interventions, or more socially focused, self-directed and flexible support for recovery (White et al., 2020). This transition highlights that PLE involvement has become more independent, empowering and reliant on the capacities of the PLE.

In a qualitative study into the experience of PSWs in Canada, it was mentioned that decisions about self-disclosure (timing and the extent) were a key aspect of their role as PLE (Asad & Chreim, 2016) “If in a meeting, it comes up that a client is not happy about taking medication... I can say I’ve experienced that and reflect it back to the team... You’re advocating for the client and... educating the team.”

However, meaningful engagement with PLE requires safeguards to be put in place to support their well-being. Psychological safety for PSWs was a key consideration, necessitating structured training and ongoing organisational support to prevent burnout and emotional strain (Ben-Dor et al., 2024). Furthermore, organisational engagement was identified as a critical facilitator in ensuring the successful integration of PLEs within the intervention. The active involvement of mental health workers and management was essential to providing PLE facilitators with the necessary institutional backing and space to effectively carry out their roles (Ibrahim et al., 2020). These findings underscore the importance of structured, intentional, and reciprocal engagement of PLEs to ensure their involvement in PSIs is both meaningful and sustainable.

Therefore, UPSIDES was also built on the premise of PLE supporting others going through similar issues in their recovery journey (Nixdorf et al., 2024). Therefore, PLEs and co-production are central to the UPSIDES project, where PSWs are directly leading the intervention development and scaling, including research. In interviews, this was emphasised as a key aspect of UPSIDES, with the view that this is a PLE-led intervention at all levels, including through a PLE-led international advisory board and local advisory boards in each site (Charles et al., 2022). PLEs were a critical part of the initial UPSIDES TOC consultations during the development phase of the interventions (Nixdorf et al., 2022).

This process was described by a key implementor in Uganda: “Yes, the peer support program at Butabika Hospital was developed in close collaboration with people with lived experience. Their insights were critical in shaping the program’s design, implementation, and evaluation. This collaborative approach ensured that the intervention was culturally appropriate, relevant, and responsive to the needs of the individuals it aimed to serve.”

The UPSIDES project recognises that PSWs have been instrumental in fostering recovery and reducing stigma associated with mental health disorders (Ramesh et al., 2023). The engagement of PLEs to share their journeys with others experiencing similar circumstances has been inspiring, giving hope and empowering (Ibrahim et al., 2020).

According to a senior psychiatrist in Uganda: “At Butabika Hospital, we have observed improved treatment adherence, enhanced social functioning, and increased self-efficacy among participants. Peer support also complements clinical care by addressing psychosocial needs that are often overlooked in traditional treatment models.”

In a qualitative study (Nixdorf et al., 2022), one PSW from Ulm mentioned, “*The first two or three appointments were very difficult in that area. But then we got used to each other. Then [the service user] always came to the appointment with a smile.*”

Within the UPSIDES project, training and capacity building were identified as crucial elements for equipping PSWs with the necessary skills and confidence to support others in their recovery journeys. The UPSIDES training program was co-facilitated with PLEs, ensuring that they not only provided support but also developed confidence in advocating for mental health rights (C. Mahlke et al., 2020). To enhance accessibility, the training manual was designed using activity-based, simple tools that could be effectively used by lay facilitators, incorporating feedback from PLEs during its development (C. Mahlke et al., 2020). An essential component of this training was preparing PSWs for self-disclosure, a critical aspect of peer

support, by equipping them with the necessary skills to share their experiences safely and meaningfully (Ben-Dor et al., 2024).

A fundamental principle of the UPSIDES model is to challenge traditional hierarchies within mental health services by ensuring that training is not solely led by mental health professionals but instead facilitated in an equal and reciprocal manner between professionals and peer trainers (C. Mahlke et al., 2020). This approach not only validated the expertise of PLEs but also contributed to shifting perceptions about mental health knowledge, positioning lived experience as a valuable form of expertise.

Evidence generated through the UPSIDES project has been collated by the UPSIDES consortium and published by the scientists, mental health professionals, and stakeholders involved. The authors of these publications represent their institutional affiliations, and their PLE status is unknown. However, the final UPSIDES manual has recognised the PSWs from each study site.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Resource requirements for general PSIs vary based on the typology of the intervention and context of implementation. However, within the health system the use of PSW is considered to be lower cost in comparison to degree-qualified health professionals (Pitt et al., 2013). Some studies noted absenteeism and challenges in retaining peer supporters due to the work being too stressful, training being too lengthy, travel distance, and the negative effect of employment on welfare benefits (Pitt et al., 2013). Most studies identified that training and ongoing supervision of PSWs to be important; however, lengthy training was considered one of the barriers to retaining staff, while some PSWs felt they had received insufficient training for their role (Pitt et al., 2013).

When considering severe mental health conditions, peer support is considered to significantly reduce hospital bed use, with the average financial savings outweighing additional costs of employing PSWs (benefit: cost ratio of 4.76:1), highlighting the cost-effectiveness of peer support (Trachtenberg et al., 2013). A systematic review on PSIs identified that only one out of the nineteen trials included in the review considered cost, but the trial was not sufficiently powered to draw any conclusions (Simpson et al., 2014). According to the study, the total cost per case for the peer support arm of the study was £2154 compared to £1922 for the control arm. The mean difference between costs was minimal and not statistically significant. However, further analyses demonstrated that peer support has a reasonably high probability of being more cost-effective for a modest positive change in the measure of hopelessness.

A 96-week pragmatic RCT, conducted in NHS primary care compared psychoeducation (PEd) with peer support. Accordingly participants receiving PEd (n=153) used more (costly) health-related resources than peer support (n=151) (net cost per person £1098 (95% CI, £252-£1943)), with a quality-adjusted life year (QALY) gain of 0.023 (95% CI, 0.001-0.056). The cost per QALY gained was £47,739. While these results indicate the cost-effectiveness of PSIs, it should be noted that there is a high level of uncertainty in the data and results (Camacho et al., 2017). Furthermore, an RCT across six crisis resolution teams in England evaluated a PSW self-management intervention (n=221) against the usual care (n=220) and found a significant reduction in admissions to acute mental healthcare for participants receiving the intervention (Le Novere et al., 2023). The probability that the PSW intervention was cost-effective compared with usual care at 12 months varied with the method used, and ranged from 57% to 96% at a cost-effectiveness threshold of £20,000 per QALY gained (Le Novere et al., 2023).

Resource requirements for implementing UPSIDES depend on contextual factors (M. Haun et al., 2024). These include the local partner's previous experience of working with PSW, social perceptions on the potential contributions of PSWs (reduction of burden on MH workforce) and allocation of sufficient resources, especially in LMICs (M. Haun et al., 2024).

UPSIDES also highlights the need for training and preparation of PSWs to deliver the intervention. During the UPSIDES project, participants in study sites with lower resources and lower levels of education (Tanzania and Uganda), reported that the transfer of formal knowledge was an essential training component that enabled PSWs to perform their tasks (M. Haun et al., 2024). In this case formal knowledge refers to evidence and basic conceptual understanding of the UPSIDES model and lessons from other settings. PSW view this as important for legitimising their own work, especially as they may not have had access to education in their own setting. In a qualitative evaluation, a PSW in Kampala mentioned that “It [the training] was very vital, guided me, helped me explore my wellness, and how to help others”(Nixdorf et al., 2022).

As such the training manual developed through a consultative process consists of simple activities and facilitated learning sessions that are easily trainable for lay PSWs and delivered in low-resource settings. The low dependence on technology makes the intervention accessible in low-resource settings. Furthermore, the training is designed to accommodate 16 participants per session in an accessible and safe environment where they can freely engage and express themselves. The implementers of the programme need to ensure that such logistics are made available to implement UPSIDES training.

However, the contextualisation process of UPSIDES using the 10-step Proportionate Translation Methodology (as described above) can be resource-intensive, especially when adapting to a new context. Once the training materials are adapted and PSW training conducted, the site-based implementation and scaling seem to demand fewer financial resources and pose a limited burden on the health system, enabling scale-up in an existing context to be more feasible. There are diverse approaches to remuneration of PSW in practice, however, with some countries also insisting on doing this to maintain motivation (see scalability section).

A cost-effectiveness analysis is one of the objectives of the UPSIDES-RCT but that data has not been published yet.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Historically, most studies on PSI have been carried out in HICs (Ibrahim et al., 2020). In contrast, the UPSIDES project aims to compare the intervention in low–middle and high-income country settings (Nixdorf et al., 2024).

A qualitative analysis across the six UPSIDES study sites with the participation of 54 key informants (M. Haun et al., 2024) indicates that UPSIDES is an intervention applicable in diverse settings. The study also highlighted that the adaptability of the study in each setting depended on the considerations given to contextual factors when implementing PSIs. Accordingly, it was noted that differing organisational cultures lead to differences in role expectations, and issues of professionalism and practice boundaries/opportunities set for PSWs (Charles et al., 2020).

It also highlighted the need to engage with staff and professionals in the context, especially in low-resource settings to ensure they understand the potential benefits and support the intervention. For the UPSIDES project, engagement of stakeholders varied across study sites and was seen either as a barrier (low engagement) or a facilitator (high engagement) depending on the context.

“The hospital managers will benefit, the staff on the ward will benefit, the service users will benefit and the PSWs will benefit. **If it’s well managed**, it will be a win-win situation.” (BU 45, pre-intervention FGD).

Benefits for health workers include a reduced workload as PSW pick up some tasks. PSWs may also help increase access to the intervention, and by having more time for individual follow-up, could also support

adherence. However, if PSI practices are not streamlined into the general processes for MH care, benefits may be inconsistent.

Certain cultural factors were also recognized as barriers to the intervention such as stigma and beliefs about mental illnesses and the potential of PLEs to contribute meaningfully in addressing illness which they attribute to spiritual causes: “(...) *Some families might not support PSW as they believe mental illness can be treated spiritually.*” (DS 84, pre-intervention FGD).

Across study sites, adequate training of peer support workers was seen as a crucial factor and a facilitator for implementation. “*Peer support workers have a change of perspective from client to employee. And that’s a difficult thing. You have to teach it to people.*” (ULM 26, pre-intervention FGD).

The intervention manual is a key tool to ensure that the training of PSWs can be conducted relatively easily and with increased fidelity across different contexts. This also enables a foundation for the intervention to be adapted to new settings by translating and contextualizing the training manual. The manualized nature of the intervention also increases its scalability.

The implementation of UPSIDES varied from site to site, in that the intervention may variably link with national health systems or organisations. At some study sites (Hamburg, Ulm), participants reported that UPSIDES was implemented independently of existing structures as a stand-alone intervention at a psychiatry unit or medical clinic of a hospital where there is limited interaction and coordination between PSWs and MHWs. At other sites, UPSIDES was perceived as well-integrated in the organisational setting, such as a community centre (Israel) or mental health clinic (India) where the PSWs serve as part of the care team at the setting. In these settings, UPSIDES was well received and supported by different stakeholders, including managers, hospital administration and nurses.

According to a qualitative study with key informants (M. Haun et al., 2024), across all the study sites, participants reported changes through UPSIDES were mostly seen at an individual level, showing that the intervention had positive effects on the service users and PSWs, including improved hope, empowerment and social inclusion. However, sustainability of the intervention at the study sites beyond the project end-date seem to vary based on past experiences of engaging with PSIs, perceived benefit to the organisation and importance given to PSIs by the workforce.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

Equity is a core consideration in all PSIs, as these approaches are inherently designed to centre the voices and experiences of PLE of mental health conditions who are often marginalised within traditional health and social systems. By engaging PSWs from diverse backgrounds, PSIs attempt to address structural inequities related to race, class, gender, and disability. Furthermore, PSIs promote more inclusive care by reducing power imbalances between providers and service users, fostering mutuality and respect (Nixdorf et al., 2022). However, equity challenges remain, particularly in ensuring fair compensation, access to training, and meaningful integration of PSWs within hierarchical healthcare systems. Additionally, most evidence for PSIs originates from HICs, raising questions about equity in global access and the cultural adaptability of interventions in LMIC settings.

In considering the above, UPSIDES project has been engaging with PLEs as co-designers, trainers and implementers, helping balance the power between service users and professionals. It also empowered PLEs to play an active role in recovery of service users even in challenging times such as during COVID-19 (Goldfarb et al., 2024). However, this also meant that there was a lot of expectation and responsibility on the PSWs. This could lead to a considerable burden to support the recovery of their peers while

managing the challenges of the mental health conditions they themselves face. UPSIDES emphasised the need for supportive environments and facilitated this via an online peer community.

Across UPSIDES implementation sites, PSWs don't tend to be formal cadres nor have a professional status. As such, there are inequalities in terms of access to mobile technologies (devices/data), financial stability, secure employment and benefits, increasing the vulnerability of the PSWs. This is especially true in vulnerable situations when they and their peers are also at their most isolated (Mpango et al., 2020). For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the peer supporters continued to provide support while the service providers also faced similar risks and vulnerabilities as those facing an active mental health condition (Mpango et al., 2020). Benefits for PSWs are not standardised across PSIs. For example, Uganda's PSWs are not salaried employees and instead combine small incentives such as meals and transport allowances with income-generating activities such as farming or petty trading to make ends meet. During COVID-19 lockdowns, their livelihoods were under threat, and restricted access to the services upon which many PSWs rely to support their own recovery. In addition, PSWs were unable to meet fellow PSWs or the peers whom they support and who were often facing similar challenges, contributing to loneliness and isolation, and ultimately to the deterioration of some PSWs' mental health (Mpango et al., 2020). In contrast, the PSWs in India (called "peer support volunteers", or "PSVs") were hired through the Department of Health and Family Welfare as part of the Government of Gujarat's mental health policy, putting PSVs in a less financially precarious situation. However, this also meant that peer support was treated like other hospital-based services and did not extend into the community.

Gender disparities are also evident. PSWs in many PSIs, including UPSIDES, are predominantly women (M. Haun et al., 2024; M. H. Haun et al., 2024), raising concerns about reinforcing unpaid care burdens and widening the gender pay gap. Furthermore, the gender imbalance may discourage men from seeking support.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

The UPSIDES project represents a significant effort in scaling up PSIs across high-, middle-, and low-resource settings, with the goal of improving access to mental health care and recovery-oriented approaches. However, the expansion of such interventions encounters various barriers and facilitators that impact their sustainability and effectiveness.

One of the key facilitators of the UPSIDES project has been the early and sustained engagement of organisational management, mental health professionals, and key stakeholders. This proactive involvement is key for fostering acceptance of peer support workers (PSWs) within mental health service settings, thereby mitigating their potential marginalisation. Furthermore, the development of a structured training program, including a comprehensive training manual and ongoing supervision, has ensured that PSWs are well-equipped to deliver the intervention with confidence and consistency. The participatory, activity-based training model employed by UPSIDES enhances the accessibility of the intervention for individuals with diverse educational backgrounds, thereby improving its scalability.

Additionally, the strong co-design element of the intervention—developed through extensive consultation—ensures that it remains culturally relevant and contextually appropriate, thereby facilitating smoother implementation. As a multi-country initiative, the establishment of a cross-site training platform (www.upsides-community.org) has further enabled knowledge sharing and the development of an international peer support network, which has contributed to the overall quality and fidelity of the intervention. The platform was set up and served as a point of contact and exchange for the trainers and PSWs during the main study period. It is envisioned for the platform to be further developed in order to

facilitate the training of further UPSIDES peer support trainers all over the world as a way of contributing to the sustainability of the intervention.

One key barrier to the eventual adoption of the intervention concerns its integration with existing organisations and systems. According to the UPSIDES, to reap the best benefits of peer-to-peer interventions, PSWs need to be placed in services that place a value on lived experience as a resource benefiting others (Ibrahim et al., 2020). In return the presence of PSWs in the service delivery system will reduce in-system stigma and 'them-and-us' distinctions, thereby reducing inequalities.

UPSIDES has demonstrated the highest levels of effectiveness in settings where PSWs are recognised as integral members of multidisciplinary teams. In such environments, PSWs contribute to shifting organisational culture towards more recovery-oriented models of care, leading to benefits such as improved task-sharing, reduced clinical workload, and increased treatment adherence.

In terms of barriers to implementation, one of the primary challenges is resistance from healthcare institutions and professionals regarding the integration of PSWs. This resistance is often exacerbated by a lack of clarity, biases and previous understandings surrounding the roles and scope of PSWs within mental health service delivery, which can significantly impede the intervention's effectiveness.

Moreover, the stigma surrounding mental health conditions, coupled with scepticism regarding the capacity of PSWs to make meaningful contributions to care, presents a substantial barrier. In certain cultural contexts, there is a reluctance to engage with peer-led interventions, with a preference for alternative forms of support, such as spiritual or traditional healing practices.

Financial instability is another critical barrier, as PSWs often work under informal or precarious service arrangements, receiving minimal financial remuneration or benefits. This lack of financial security can contribute to burnout and reduced motivation among PSWs, particularly during crises or disasters when they are expected to provide continued support with minimal institutional backing. Additionally, given that PSWs have personal lived experiences with mental health conditions, they may face similar challenges as the individuals they support, further complicating their role.

Gender disparities within the PSWs also present a challenge, as they are predominantly women. This can exacerbate existing gender inequalities in caregiving roles, particularly in contexts where unpaid or underpaid care work is disproportionately shouldered by women.

While PSIs are widely regarded as cost-effective, the limited availability of robust economic analyses on their long-term financial sustainability presents an obstacle to securing greater investment in these interventions. Further research and cost-effectiveness evaluations are necessary to strengthen the case for scaling up PSIs within mental health systems globally.

Recommendations for investment:

Interest in PSIs is growing globally, and evidence-based approaches are essential for adapting the PSW role to meet local needs while preserving its integrity. UPSIDES, as one of the most robust PSI, has been trialled in low-, middle-, and high-income settings, with strong qualitative data supporting the potential benefit of the intervention. However, its acceptability and scalability are still unclear due to effectiveness and efficacy data not yet being published.

The following recommendations focus on PSIs in general:

Research Recommendations

- **Expand the Evidence Base in LMICs:** The evidence base is predominantly focused on HICs, so further investment in rigorous implementation research and cost-effectiveness studies to assess the feasibility, sustainability, and cultural relevance of PSIs in low-resource settings is needed.
- **Invest in evidence to identify effective peer support modalities and their adaptability to new contexts:** Further research is needed to determine how best to integrate PSWs into formal systems, define accreditation pathways, embed them in crisis response, and align peer support with national health policies, especially in diverse and under-researched settings.
- **Review of intervention typology:** Facilitate a thorough review of different PSI types to understand intervention models suited for different contexts; realist evaluation methods could identify most effective ways to scale and adopt approaches in new health systems.

Ecosystem Recommendations

- **Standardisation surrounding roles, scope of practice:** Cross-country PLE led dialogue on the state of evidence and lived experiences of PSWs and PLE across settings can advance sharing of lessons. Such dialogue can help clarify the scope of PSI and PSW roles and practice in different contexts and provide a starting point for other developers in this space.
- **Consider Digital Platforms for Peer Support and Supervision:** It may be possible to use low-bandwidth digital tools (e.g. WhatsApp-integrated apps) to enable supervision, learning, and peer connection, especially in rural or underserved regions. However, this requires not only research, but also dialogue as noted above prior to promotion.
- **Ensure Fair Compensation and Protections:** Finally, it must be acknowledged that PSW are workers, but that in many contexts their work remains formally unrecognised or remunerated. Policy dialogue on this – also as linked to Community Health Workers policies – could help identify where/how establish formal employment pathways is possible. The combination of PSI with supported employment interventions could be considered.

The following recommendations focus on the UPSIDES intervention:

Research Recommendations

- **Publish Clinical and Economic Outcomes:** Accelerate the release of clinical and psychosocial outcome data and conduct robust cost-effectiveness analyses, particularly in LMIC contexts.
- **Assess Broader Applicability:** Evaluate UPSIDES' effectiveness among individuals with mild to moderate mental health conditions to explore its scalability beyond severe mental illness.
- **Strengthen the evidence base on implementation supports and inclusive practices for PSWs:** More research is needed to understand how best to promote PSW wellbeing through supervision and support, ensure gender equity and cultural inclusion, and expand delivery models to community-based, non-clinical settings.

Ecosystems Recommendations

- **Strengthen the Global Training Infrastructure:** Further develop the UPSIDES training portal to support continuous training of PSWs and trainers across diverse settings.
- **Develop an Innovation Lab for Peer Support:** Building on the training portal, create a cross-country innovation hub to co-design and test localised adaptations, such as mobile-first models or youth- and gender-specific formats.
- **Integrate PSWs into Mental Health Governance:** Involve trained PSWs in policy-making forums and service planning to embed lived experience in system-level decisions.

Key references:

- Asad, S., & Chreim, S. (2016). Peer Support Providers' Role Experiences on Interprofessional Mental Health Care Teams: A Qualitative Study. *Community Mental Health Journal*, 52(7), 767–774. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10597-015-9970-5>
- Camacho, E. M., Ntais, D., Jones, S., Riste, L., Morriss, R., Lobban, F., & Davies, L. M. (2017). Cost-effectiveness of structured group psychoeducation versus unstructured group support for bipolar disorder: Results from a multi-centre pragmatic randomised controlled trial. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 211, 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2017.01.005>
- Charles, A., Korde, P., Newby, C., Grayzman, A., Hiltensperger, R., Mahlke, C., Moran, G., Nakku, J., Niwemuhwezi, J., Nixdorf, R., Paul, E., Puschner, B., Ramesh, M., Ryan, G. K., Shamba, D., Kalha, J., & Slade, M. (2022). *Proportionate translation of study materials and measures in a multinational global health trial: Methodology development and implementation*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-058083>
- Charles, A., Thompson, D., Nixdorf, R., Ryan, G., Shamba, D., Kalha, J., Moran, G., Hiltensperger, R., Mahlke, C., Puschner, B., Repper, J., Slade, M., & Mpango, R. (2020). Typology of modifications to peer support work for adults with mental health problems: Systematic review. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 216(6), 301–307. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.2019.264>
- Goldfarb, Y., Grayzman, A., Meir, L. G., Grundman, S. H., Rabinian, M., Lachman, M., Epstein, P. G., Ben-Dor, I. A., Naaman, A., Puschner, B., & Moran, G. S. (2024). UPSIDES Mental Health Peer Support in Face of the COVID-19 Pandemic: Actions and Insights. *Community Mental Health Journal*, 60(1), 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10597-022-01030-9>
- Haun, M. H., Girit, S., Goldfarb, Y., Kalha, J., Korde, P., Kwebiha, E., Moran, G., Mtei, R., Niwemuhwezi, J., Nixdorf, R., Nugent, L., Puschner, B., Ramesh, M., Ryan, G. K., Slade, M., Charles, A., & Krumm, S. (2024). *Mental health workers' perspectives on the implementation of a peer support intervention in five countries: Qualitative findings from the UPSIDES study*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2023-081963>
- Haun, M., Adler Ben-Dor, I., Hall, C., Kalha, J., Korde, P., Moran, G., Müller-Stierlin, A. S., Niwemuhwezi, J., Nixdorf, R., Puschner, B., Ramesh, M., Charles, A., & Krumm, S. (2024). Perspectives of key informants before and after implementing UPSIDES peer support in mental health services: Qualitative findings from an international multi-site study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 24(1), 159. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-024-10543-w>
- Hiltensperger, R., Ryan, G., Ben-Dor, I. A., Charles, A., Epple, E., Kalha, J., Korde, P., Kotera, Y., Mpango, R., Moran, G., Mueller-Stierlin, A. S., Nixdorf, R., Ramesh, M., Shamba, D., Slade, M., Puschner, B., & Nakku, J. (2024). Implementation of peer support for people with severe mental health conditions in high-, middle- and low-income-countries: A theory of change approach. *BMC Health Services Research*, 24(1), 480. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-024-10990-5>
- Ibrahim, N., Thompson, D., Nixdorf, R., Kalha, J., Mpango, R., Moran, G., Mueller-Stierlin, A., Ryan, G., Mahlke, C., Shamba, D., Puschner, B., Repper, J., & Slade, M. (2020). A systematic review of influences on implementation of peer support work for adults with mental health problems. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 55(3), 285–293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-019-01739-1>
- *Imroc*. (n.d.). Imroc. Retrieved March 11, 2025, from <https://www.imroc.org>
- Johnson, S., Lamb, D., Marston, L., Osborn, D., Mason, O., Henderson, C., Ambler, G., Milton, A., Davidson, M., Christoforou, M., Sullivan, S., Hunter, R., Hindle, D., Paterson, B., Leverton, M., Piotrowski, J., Forsyth, R., Mosse, L., Goater, N., ... Lloyd-Evans, B. (2018). Peer-supported self-management for people discharged from a mental health crisis team: A randomised controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 392(10145), 409–418. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31470-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31470-3)
- Le Novere, M., Johnson, S., Lloyd-Evans, B., Marston, L., Ambler, G., Clarke, C. S., Osborn, D., Lamb, D., & Hunter, R. M. (2023). Cost-effectiveness of peer-supported self-management for people discharged from a mental health crisis team: Methodological challenges and recommendations. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14, 1031159. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1031159>
- Lloyd-Evans, B., Mayo-Wilson, E., Harrison, B., Istead, H., Brown, E., Pilling, S., Johnson, S., & Kendall, T. (2014). A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials of peer support for people with severe mental illness.

- BMC Psychiatry, 14, 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-14-39>
- Mahlke, C. I., Priebe, S., Heumann, K., Daubmann, A., Wegscheider, K., & Bock, T. (2017). Effectiveness of one-to-one peer support for patients with severe mental illness – a randomised controlled trial. *European Psychiatry*, 42, 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2016.12.007>
 - Mahlke, C., Nixdorf, R., Repper, J., Charles, A., Slade, M., Ryan, G., Hall, C., Baillie, D., Hiltensperger, R., Müller-Stierlin, A., Nakku, J., Mpango, R., Shamba, D., Ramesh, M., Garber-Epstein, P., Moran, G. S., Kalha, J., Korde, P., Puschner, B., & UPSIDES Peer Support Trainers. (2020). *UPSIDES Peer Support Worker Training Manual and Workbook*. UPSIDES Study.
 - Moran, G. S., Kalha, J., Mueller-Stierlin, A. S., Kilian, R., Krumm, S., Slade, M., Charles, A., Mahlke, C., Nixdorf, R., Basangwa, D., Nakku, J., Mpango, R., Ryan, G., Shamba, D., Ramesh, M., Ngakongwa, F., Grayzman, A., Pathare, S., Mayer, B., & Puschner, B. (2020). Peer support for people with severe mental illness versus usual care in high-, middle- and low-income countries: Study protocol for a pragmatic, multicentre, randomised controlled trial (UPSIDES-RCT). *Trials*, 21(1), 371. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-020-4177-7>
 - Mpango, R., Kalha, J., Shamba, D., Ramesh, M., Ngakongwa, F., Kulkarni, A., Korde, P., Nakku, J., & Ryan, G. K. (2020). Challenges to peer support in low- and middle-income countries during COVID-19. *Globalization and Health*, 16(1), 90. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-020-00622-y>
 - Pitt, V., Lowe, D., Hill, S., Prictor, M., Hetrick, S. E., Ryan, R., & Berends, L. (2013). Consumer-providers of care for adult clients of statutory mental health services. The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, 2013(3), CD004807. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD004807.pub2>
 - Simmons, M. B., Cartner, S., MacDonald, R., Whitson, S., Bailey, A., & Brown, E. (2023). The effectiveness of peer support from a person with lived experience of mental health challenges for young people with anxiety and depression: A systematic review. *BMC Psychiatry*, 23(1), 194. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-04578-2>
 - Trachtenberg, M., Parsonage, M., Shepherd, G., & Boardman, J. (2013). Peer support in mental health care: Is it good value for money? (LSE Research Online Documents on Economics) [Working paper]. London School of Economics and Political Science, LSE Library. <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:ehl:lserod:60793>